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D5.1 ENTRUST Blockchain Architecture, Authorization and Secure On- and Off-Chain Data Management – First Release

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Abstract	<p>Deliverable D5.1 documents the first releases of the ENTRUST Blockchain Architecture, Authorization and Secure On- and Off-Chain Data Management. D5.1 thoroughly analyses ENTRUST's Blockchain Architecture and the Tracer enabling the secure management of CMDs in the ENTRUST Framework. More specifically, D5.1 presents the landscape of Blockchain types and platforms and their use in the medical domain towards selecting the most suitable Blockchain network. Then, it defines the requirements for the ENTRUST Blockchain and Tracer and provides the ENTRUST Blockchain Architecture along with the definition of smart contracts that will facilitate the storage and retrieval of sensitive medical device data towards establishing the trustworthiness of CMDs. The functionalities of the Tracer that enable the tracing operations in high- and low-end medical devices are also specified. Finally, D5.1 defines the research plan for the development of functionalities for the second releases of the ENTRUST Blockchain and the Tracer.</p>		
Keywords	Blockchain Infrastructure, DLT, Smart Contracts, Architecture, CMD Monitoring, Tracer		

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PU	Public, fully open	x
SEN	Sensitive, confidential to ENTRUST project and Commission Services	

- * R: Document, report (excluding the periodic and final reports)
- DEM: Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs
- DEC: Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.
- OTHER: Software, technical diagram, etc.
- DMP: Data Management Plan

Glossary of terms and abbreviations used

Term	Description
ABAC	Attribute-Based Access Control
ABE	Attribute-Based Encryption
ABS	Attribute-Based Signature
AI	Artificial Intelligence
API	Application Technology Interface
ATL	Actual Trust Level
BC	Blockchain
BCC	BPF Compiler Collection
BLE	Bluetooth Low Energy
BPF	Berkeley Packet Filter
CA	Certificate Authority
CC	Conformity Certificate
CFG	Control Flow Graph
CFI	Control Flow Integrity
CMD	Connected Medical Device
CPU	Central Processing Unit
DAG	Directed Acyclic Graph
DApp	Decentralized Application
DeFi	Decentralized Finance
DK	Development Kit
DLT	Distributed Ledger Technology
DPoS	Delegated Proof of Stake
Dx.y	Deliverable x.y
eBPF	Extended Berkeley Packet Filter
ECDSA	Elliptic Curve Digital Signature Algorithm
eIDAS	Electronic Identification, Authentication, and Trust Services
eMUD	Extended Manufacturer Usage Description
ETH	Ether
EVM	Ethereum Virtual Machine
FHIR	Fast Healthcare Interoperability Resources
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
gRPC	Google Remote Procedure Call
HLF	Hyperledger Fabric

HW	Hardware
ID	Identity
IDM	Identity Management
IEC	International Electrotechnical Commission
I/O	Input/Output
IoT	Internet of Things
IP	Internet Protocol
ISMS	Information Security Management System
ISO/IEC	International Organization for Standardization
ISR	Interrupt Service Routine
IT	Information Technology
JIT	Just-In-Time
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
Mx	Month x
MSP	Membership Service Provider
NFT	Non-Fungible Token
OEM	Original Equipment Manufacturer
OOP	Object-Oriented Programming
PABC	Privacy Attribute-Based Credentials
PAP	Policy Administration Point
PBFT	Practical Byzantine Fault Tolerance
PDP	Policy Decision Point
PEP	Policy Enforcement Point
PIP	Policy Information Point
PoA	Proof of Authority
PoC	Proof of Capacity
PoET	Proof of Elapsed Time
PoS	Proof of Stake
PoW	Proof of Work
PUF	Physical Unclonable Function
RA	Risk Assessment
RTL	Required Trust Level
RTOS	Real-Time Operating System
SC	Smart Contract
SCB	Security Context Broker

SCG	Service Graph Chain
SSI	Self-Sovereign Identity
STIX	Structured Threat Information Expression
SW	Software
TAF	Trust Assessment Framework
TCB	Trusted Computing Base
TCP	Transmission Control Protocol
URL	Uniform Resource Locator
VC	Verifiable Credential
VM	Virtual Machine
VP	Verifiable Presentation
WPx	Work Package x

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Executive Summary

ENTRUST aims to develop a comprehensive framework for ensuring the security, privacy and operational assurance of Connected Medical Devices (CMDs) within healthcare organizations. Towards this endmost goal, the Blockchain technology is leveraged due to its inherent characteristics of **decentralization and immutability**. In addition, apart from these characteristics, leveraging Blockchain technology (a) provide **auditability and integrity of data transactions**, which is crucial for establishing trust among entities, (b) supports the **enforcement of policies in an auditable and verifiable manner** and (c) assist the **efficient certifiability of the medical devices** through the storage of Conformity Certificates (CC) assisted by the privacy-preserving threat intelligence sharing.

The deliverable D5.1 “ENTRUST Blockchain Architecture, Authorization and Secure On- and Off-Chain Data Management – First Release” constitutes a direct outcome of the Task 5.1 “Blockchain Design and Services Specification”, Task 5.2 “Enforcement of Distributed Trust Framework and Smart Contracts for Lifecycle Management of Medical Devices”, Task 5.3 “Trust-aware Authentication and Authorization” and Task 5.4 “CMD Evidence Monitoring Collection”, documenting the alpha releases of the **ENTRUST Blockchain Infrastructure** and the **Tracer** component that play a pivotal role in the **establishment of trustworthiness of connected medical devices in the ENTRUST framework**.

The use of Blockchain networks in the medical domain is presented and a thorough state-of-the-art analysis of different Blockchain types and technologies, smart contracts and consensus algorithms are elaborated. Also, the need for secure and strong Identity Management (IDM) and access control mechanisms are described, showcasing the approach of ENTRUST in leveraging Self-Sovereign Identity (SSI) models with Verifiable Credentials (VCs) and Attribute-based Access Control (ABAC) functionalities for prohibiting unauthorized access in the medical device data stored in the ENTRUST DLT. In this context, the Hyperledger Fabric is selected as the most suitable Blockchain technology for the ENTRUST Blockchain Infrastructure.

The data types that will be used in the ENTRUST Blockchain and the Tracer are identified, along with the dedicated data-sharing workflows that accommodate trust policies, attestation data, application data and network logs, Conformity Certificates (CC) and eMUDs. The data lifecycle management in the ENTRUST DLT is defined, pinpointing the adherence to regulations and standards such as GDPR and FHIR. Moreover, the privacy, security and trust requirements that embrace the design and development of the ENTRUST Blockchain and the Tracer are described. Initially, the general requirements that govern the operation of these components are provided followed by more specific requirements that concern certain aspects of the function of the ENTRUST Blockchain and the Tracer, such as confidentiality and integrity, data trustworthiness and access control.

In addition, the architecture of the **ENTRUST Blockchain Infrastructure** is presented, describing all the internal operations needed for maintaining an up-to-date view of the trustworthiness level of both the device- and domain-level service-graph-chains: (a) **Preparing the Device for Trustworthiness Establishment**, (b) **Establishing Device Trustworthiness** and (c) **Re-establishing Device Trustworthiness**. The architectural building blocks of ENTRUST Blockchain Infrastructure are also presented, showcasing their operation and how they are interconnected to enable the secure management of medical devices. The different smart contracts employed in Blockchain DLT are defined, explaining also the way they are deployed and executed.

Furthermore, the operation of the Tracer is described, where the Extended Berkeley Packet Filter (eBPF) is exploited for tracing the operation of medical devices. More specifically, the data

structure of the static and runtime properties that form the baseline for the attestation process are monitored by the Tracer, while the function of the Tracer in high-end and low-end devices is described thoroughly. Last but not least, the research plan specifying the functionalities that will be implemented and evaluated in the second release of the ENTRUST Blockchain and the Tracer is also outlined.

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose and scope of the document

ENTRUST endmost goal is to provide a comprehensive framework for ensuring the security, privacy and operational assurance of Connected Medical Devices (CMDs) within healthcare organizations. The core building block towards achieving this goal is the adoption of the Blockchain technology due to its decentralized and immutable nature. On top of that, leveraging Blockchain technology (a) provide **auditability and integrity of data flows**, which is a core aspect for trust establishment, (b) supports **auditability and verifiability** of stored trust policies and (c) reinforces **certifiability of the medical devices** in an efficient and scalable by storing the generated Conformity Certificates (CC).

Deliverable D5.1 documents the first releases of the **ENTRUST Blockchain Architecture and Tracer**, which facilitate the **secure management of medical devices in the ENTRUST framework**. As the security, trustworthiness and integrity of medical devices in the healthcare domain is critical, Blockchain technology and Tracer introduce decisive ways to safeguard the operation of medical devices. The ENTRUST Blockchain Infrastructure facilitates the establishment of trustworthiness of connected medical devices (CMDs) by storing attestation data, trust policies, application data, Conformity Certificates (CC) and eMUDs that can be accessed only by authorized entities and can be used for the monitoring of trust management in CMDs. On top of that, the Tracer enables the identification of trust properties of CMDs and the monitoring of the values of trust properties towards verifying that the devices are in a trustworthy state.

In this document, the ENTRUST Blockchain Infrastructure is presented, starting with a thorough state-of-the-art analysis of Blockchain technologies, smart contracts and consensus algorithms that leads to the selection of the most suitable Blockchain platform for the ENTRUST DLT. The data types and data sharing workflows that are envisaged in the ENTRUST framework regarding the Blockchain and the Tracer are provided, while the management of the entire data lifecycle and the security, privacy and trust requirements for the Blockchain and the Tracer are described.

The architecture of the ENTRUST Blockchain is also defined, presenting the three different high-level architectural flows (e.g., (a) Preparing the Device for Trustworthiness Establishment, (b) Establishing Device Trustworthiness and (c) Re-establishing Device Trustworthiness) as well as the various building blocks that comprise the ENTRUST Blockchain Architecture. The smart contracts that are deployed in the Blockchain are also specified, showcasing the recording of different data sharing transactions.

Moreover, the functionalities of the Tracer are provided, showcasing the data structure of the monitoring properties and the corresponding tracing operations on high-end and low-end devices. These tracing operations are integral to attestation schemes, as they provide the necessary evidence for verifying the integrity and trustworthiness of devices, ensuring that only authenticated and secure software is running.

Finally, the deliverable provides the research plan that will drive the development of functionalities for the second release of ENTRUST Blockchain and Tracer. The potential updates and new identified functionalities will be documented in deliverable D5.2 which is the second version of this deliverable.

Figure 1: Relation of D5.1 to other WPs and Deliverables

1.2 Relation to other Work Packages and Deliverables

Deliverable D5.1, as shown in Figure 1 below, is interconnected with WP1 “Project Management” to align with the related data management guidelines, with WP2 “Requirements, Gap Analysis and Reference Trust Architecture” for the collection of initial technical requirements for the implementation of the ENTRUST Blockchain and the Tracer, with WP3 “Trust Modelling, Risk Assessment and Security-by-Design Toolbox” to receive feedback on the trust policies to be stored in the ENTRUST Blockchain, with WP4 “Runtime Attestation Mechanisms and Continuous Certification for Post-Market CMD surveillance” to collect information in the crypto-primitives for the authorization of CMDs and the encryption of sensitive data in ENTRUST Blockchain and Off-Chain storage, and with WP6 “Integration and Validation of Trust Management Framework” for the provision of input towards evaluating the overall ENTRUST Framework in the different Use Cases of the project.

More specifically, D5.1 receives input from D2.1 “ENTRUST Reference Architecture – Initial Release” setting the basis for the design and development of the first releases of the ENTRUST Blockchain and the Tracer. It also receives input from the deliverables D3.1 “Trust Abstractions & Cryptographic Anchors for CMD Secure Operation” and D4.1 “Conceptual Architecture of ENTRUST Customizable TC and Attestation Models Specifications” regarding the crypto primitives and the trust policies that will be leveraged in ENTRUST Blockchain Architecture.

The deliverable D5.1 will provide input to D6.1 “Integrated Framework (First Release) and Use Case Analysis” regarding the integration and evaluation of the first releases of the ENTRUST Blockchain and the Tracer within the first release of the ENTRUST integrated framework. It will also constitute the basis for the deliverable D5.2 “ENTRUST Continuous Authorization, Trust Management, Monitoring Mechanisms and Trust Evidence Collection” where the second releases of the ENTRUST DLT and the Tracer will be documented, accommodating new features and updates.

1.3 Structure of the document

The present deliverable is structured as follows:

- **Section 1** provides an introduction to the work documented in this deliverable, describing the main purpose and scope of the document, its structure as well as its relationship with other Work Packages (WPs) and deliverables of the ENTRUST project.
- **Section 2** presents a comprehensive state-of-the-art analysis of the Blockchain technologies led to the selection of ENTRUST’s Blockchain Infrastructure.
- **Section 3** analyses the data sharing workflows and provides security, privacy and trust requirements for both the ENTRUST Blockchain and Tracer.
- **Section 4** describes the ENTRUST Blockchain Architecture, highlighting the core three architectural flows and building blocks.
- **Section 5** defines the type of smart contracts, the smart contract functions and data structures for the ENTRUST Blockchain Architecture.
- **Section 6** describes the various functionalities of the ENTRUST Tracer in both the high- and low-end devices.
- **Section 7** outlines the research and development plan towards the second release of both the Blockchain and Tracer.
- **Section 8** concludes the deliverable.

2 ENTRUST Blockchain Infrastructure

2.1 Use of Blockchain in the Medical Domain

The integration of **Blockchain technology** in the management of medical devices offers **transformative potential, addressing critical challenges such as data security, traceability, compliance, interoperability, and operational efficiency**. This emerging need for data provenance and data trustworthiness in the medical domain, as designated by various standards, makes the exploitation of Blockchain technology imperative as it can unlock such data capabilities in the management of medical devices [1].

Medical devices generate vast amounts of sensitive data during their operation, including device performance metrics and operational logs. Ensuring the security and integrity of such data is paramount, as on the one hand, the security of the medical devices is safeguarded and on the other hand, due to the assurance of medical devices' security, the patient data that are handled by such medical devices are also tamper-proof. ISO/IEC 27001¹, which specifies requirements for an information security management system (ISMS), and ISO 80001², which provides guidelines for risk management of IT networks incorporating medical devices, are essential standards that align with Blockchain's capabilities in data security. Blockchain's decentralized and immutable ledger provides a robust solution. By distributing data across a network of nodes, Blockchain reduces the risk of data breaches. Moreover, once data are recorded on the Blockchain, they cannot be modified or deleted, ensuring the integrity of device data and maintaining accurate historical records, which aligns with ISO/IEC 27001's principles of information security and data integrity.

Blockchain technologies also allow for comprehensive tracking of medical devices throughout their lifecycle, from manufacturing to deployment and maintenance. This tracking is supported by standards such as ISO 13485³, which outlines requirements for a quality management system where an organization needs to demonstrate its ability to provide medical devices and related services that consistently meet customer and regulatory requirements. Every transaction or modification involving a medical device can be logged on the Blockchain, providing a verifiable audit trail. This enhances transparency in the supply chain, helping to detect and prevent counterfeiting. Blockchain enables detailed tracking of a medical device's usage history, maintenance records, and performance data, ensuring accountability and facilitating efficient management, in line with ISO/TR 20416⁴, which deals with post-market surveillance.

Another critical aspect of the medical device industry is compliance with regulatory standards. The immutable nature of Blockchain provides tamper-proof records that regulators can easily audit, ensuring adherence to standards and regulations, as emphasized by ISO 14971⁵, which specifies the application of risk management to medical devices. Also, Blockchain can automate

¹ <https://www.iso.org/standard/27001>

² <https://www.iso.org/standard/72026.html>

³ <https://www.iso.org/standard/59752.html>

⁴ <https://www.iso.org/standard/67942.html>

⁵ <https://www.iso.org/standard/72704.html>

compliance reporting, providing real-time updates and reducing the administrative burden on manufacturers and healthcare providers.

As medical devices often need to communicate with other systems and devices, necessitating seamless data sharing, Blockchain can facilitate interoperability by providing a standardized protocol for data exchange, ensuring compatibility across different devices and platforms. This is consistent with IEC 62304⁶, which specifies the life cycle requirements for medical device software. Moreover, the encryption and access control mechanisms of Blockchain enable secure sharing of data between authorized entities, protecting patient privacy while enabling coordinated care.

The introduction of smart contracts on Blockchain can automate various processes related to medical device management. More specifically, smart contracts can trigger automated maintenance schedules or software updates based on predefined criteria for trust management and security, ensuring that medical devices operate efficiently and safely. This aligns with the principles outlined in ISO 81001-5-1⁷, which deals with health software and health IT systems safety.

In addition, Blockchain can contribute to the enhancement of patient safety and post-market device performance monitoring. Blockchain can support real-time monitoring and reporting of device performance data, enabling proactive maintenance and quick responses to potential issues. Adverse events can be recorded on the Blockchain, providing a reliable and transparent way to track and analyse device-related incidents, improving overall safety and efficacy, in line with IEC 82304-1⁸, which covers the safety and security of health software.

2.2 State-of-the-Art Analysis and Background Technologies

Over the past decade, distributed ledger technology has advanced significantly and has found practical applications across diverse domains. Since the emergence of Bitcoin, numerous Blockchain platforms have arisen, each showcasing unique and innovative infrastructures like Ethereum, Fabric, Quorum, and others. These platforms vary in features such as consensus mechanisms, transactional efficiency, and scalability, yet they share fundamental components essential for the functional integrity and security of the Blockchain ecosystem [2].

At their essence, Blockchain architectures consist of foundational elements including blocks (such as pointers, linked lists, and chain structures), transactions, hash functions, Merkle trees and digital signatures. Moreover, the ecosystem encompasses various entities such as nodes and miners, pivotal to the network's operation and maintenance.

The sections below summarize the most widely used Blockchain types, platforms and consensus algorithms, highlight the concept of smart contracts, analyze how identity management and access control mechanisms and how privacy-aware data sharing are handled in the context of Blockchain technology.

⁶ <https://www.iso.org/standard/38421.html>

⁷ <https://www.iso.org/standard/76097.html>

⁸ <https://www.iso.org/standard/59543.html>

2.2.1 Blockchain Types and Platforms

The different Blockchain types and platforms can be categorized as follows [3]:

Permissionless Blockchains: Permissionless Blockchains operate on a decentralized network where participation is open to anyone without requiring authorization. Examples include Bitcoin and Ethereum, where anyone can join as a node, validate transactions, and contribute to the network's security. These Blockchains emphasize transparency, immutability, and censorship resistance, relying on consensus mechanisms such as Proof of Work (PoW) or Proof of Stake (PoS) to validate transactions and achieve agreement among participants. Permissionless Blockchains enable innovation and inclusivity by allowing developers to build decentralized applications (DApps) and smart contracts without permission, promoting a global ecosystem of financial and digital assets that are accessible to anyone with an internet connection.

Permissioned Blockchains: Permissioned Blockchains are characterized by restricted access to the network, limiting participation to known entities or predefined nodes. Unlike permissionless Blockchains, where anyone can join and contribute to the network, permissioned Blockchains are typically used within organizations, consortiums, or specific communities where trust and identity verification are essential. These Blockchains offer higher privacy and control over data since access rights are managed and enforced by a central authority or a predetermined group of participants. Permissioned Blockchains often employ more efficient consensus mechanisms tailored to the specific needs of the participants, leading to faster transaction processing times and scalability. This model ensures that only authorized entities can validate transactions and participate in the governance of the network, fostering a more predictable and secure environment for enterprise applications and sensitive data management.

Hybrid Blockchains: Hybrid Blockchains blend elements of both permissioned and permissionless models to leverage the benefits of each approach. These Blockchains aim to balance the need for controlled access with the advantages of decentralized participation. Typically, hybrid Blockchains are designed for applications where certain aspects require privacy, scalability, and efficient consensus mechanisms, while others benefit from transparency, openness, and inclusivity. In hybrid Blockchains, specific parts of the network may be permissioned, restricting access to authorized entities or nodes, while other segments operate in a permissionless manner, allowing anyone to participate. Examples of hybrid Blockchains include projects that integrate private channels or sidechains within a public Blockchain framework, enabling selective disclosure of information while maintaining overall network integrity and security.

Ethereum⁹: Ethereum, introduced in 2015, is a decentralized Blockchain platform that is well-known for enabling smart contracts and decentralized applications (DApps). Utilizing its own cryptocurrency, Ether (ETH), Ethereum allows developers to create self-executing smart contracts that automate the enforcement of agreements, fostering efficient and transparent processes. The platform's Ethereum Virtual Machine (EVM) runs code securely across a network of nodes through a Proof of Stake (PoS) consensus mechanism, for improved scalability, security, and energy efficiency. Driving innovation, Ethereum has given rise to a diverse ecosystem that

⁹ <https://ethereum.org/en/>

includes decentralized finance (DeFi), non-fungible tokens (NFTs), and more. This innovation redefines traditional systems by leveraging Blockchain's decentralized nature.

Hyperledger Fabric¹⁰: Hyperledger Fabric, a Blockchain framework created under the Linux Foundation's Hyperledger project, is designed for permissioned networks. Its architecture is modular, emphasizing scalability, confidentiality, and adaptability for enterprise applications. Hyperledger Fabric features a consensus mechanism with pluggable algorithms, allowing organizations to choose the most appropriate protocol for their needs. Key elements of Fabric include the Membership Service Provider (MSP) for managing identities, smart contracts referred to as "chaincode," and channels for private communications among specific network members. This structure enables the establishment of private, permissioned networks where participants can conduct secure transactions while controlling access to sensitive information. Hyperledger Fabric's robust and flexible nature makes it ideal for developing complex distributed ledger solutions across various industries. As a permissioned Blockchain framework, it prioritizes privacy and control, making it suitable for environments where access to sensitive data needs to be restricted. Unlike other platforms that rely on specialized domain-specific languages, Hyperledger Fabric allows developers to use general-purpose scripting languages like Go, Java, and Node.js to write logic. This approach increases accessibility and simplifies the development process. Additionally, the innovative Blockchain design of Hyperledger Fabric tackles issues such as nondeterminism, resource depletion and performance attacks, thereby allowing greater flexibility.

Hyperledger Besu¹¹: Hyperledger Besu is a high-grade Ethereum client designed by the Hyperledger community, specifically for enterprise use. Developed in Java, Besu provides a flexible platform for creating decentralized applications and private Blockchain networks. It supports both public Ethereum networks and private networks, giving organizations the ability to control the level of access to their network as needed. Besu accommodates various consensus algorithms, including Proof of Work (Ethash) and Proof of Authority (IBFT, Clique). Its modular design allows for straightforward customization and seamless integration with other enterprise systems. Key features of Besu include compatibility with the Ethereum Virtual Machine (EVM), advanced privacy functionalities through Tesseract, and integration with Ethereum's Permissioning Smart Contract (EIP-1344) and other permissioning systems. These features make Hyperledger Besu suitable for businesses that want to implement Ethereum-compatible solutions while focusing on privacy, security, and customized consensus mechanisms.

IOTA¹²: IOTA is a Blockchain platform that revolves around the Tangle, a directed acyclic graph (DAG). Unlike traditional Blockchains, IOTA does not use conventional blocks or miners. Instead, network participants, known as nodes, validate transactions by confirming two previous transactions. This method enhances scalability, as transaction throughput increases with network activity, making IOTA particularly well-suited for Internet of Things (IoT) applications. To ensure network security during its initial phases, IOTA utilizes a consensus mechanism known as the Coordinator. Although IOTA is efficient, it is better suited to monetary transactions.

Corda¹³: Corda is a Blockchain platform tailored for privacy-focused applications, featuring a permissioned structure ideal for handling complex business transactions while preserving data

¹⁰ <https://www.hyperledger.org/projects/fabric>

¹¹ <https://www.hyperledger.org/projects/besu>

¹² <https://www.iota.org/>

¹³ <https://corda.net/>

confidentiality. Corda is an open-source solution, coming from R3 in 2015, that emphasizes transaction privacy. It uses smart contracts to enable various business entities to conduct transactions efficiently and cost-effectively. A key aspect of Corda's architecture is its focus on privacy in transaction design. Using the "Doorman" node, which verifies identities and issues certificates, it facilitates secure and authorized data access. This design enhances data confidentiality, making Corda highly effective for enterprise environments where privacy is crucial.

Quorum¹⁴: Quorum, coming from the financial domain, is an open-source Blockchain platform based on Ethereum, tailored for high efficiency in permissioned use cases. It is ideal for handling private transactions within enterprises. Quorum's performance stands out due to its implementation of various consensus algorithms and a voting system, which enable it to process a large number of transactions per second. Furthermore, Quorum supports both private and public on-chain transactions and smart contracts, maintaining the confidentiality of sensitive data. This combination of features makes Quorum suitable for environments where preserving data privacy is essential.

EOS¹⁵: EOS is a Blockchain platform focused on delivering high throughput and scalability for decentralized applications (DApps) and smart contracts. It utilizes a Delegated Proof of Stake (DPoS) consensus mechanism, where 21 elected block producers handle transaction validation and network security. This design allows for rapid transaction confirmations and efficient processing, though it sacrifices some decentralization compared to other consensus models. In EOS, users stake EOS tokens to access network resources like CPU and RAM, which helps manage congestion and ensures consistent costs. The platform employs a WebAssembly (WASM) virtual machine to execute smart contracts, enhancing flexibility and supporting multiple programming languages. EOSIO, the underlying software, provides developers with a toolkit and libraries for building complex DApps, including features for authentication, authorization and cross-Blockchain communication.

Avalanche¹⁶: Avalanche stands out as a Blockchain platform featuring the innovative Avalanche consensus protocol and Subnets architecture. The Avalanche consensus protocol utilizes a unique "randomized sampling" approach, employing repeated rounds of voting to achieve rapid consensus. This methodology ensures high throughput and minimal latency, catering well to applications requiring swift transaction confirmation. Its Subnets architecture allows for the customization of consensus configurations within the same network, supporting diverse use cases and enabling developers to tailor consensus mechanisms according to specific requirements. Validators have the capability to participate in multiple subnets concurrently, enhancing the flexibility of the network. With its robust technical foundation, including Byzantine fault tolerance, Avalanche offers a dependable solution for decentralized applications seeking scalability, rapid finality, and configurable consensus algorithms.

2.2.2 Smart Contracts

Smart contracts, first proposed by Nick Szabo [4] and later brought to prominence through the Ethereum Blockchain. Smart contracts are self-operating agreements where the contract terms are embedded directly into software code. These contracts are a significant advancement in

¹⁴ <https://www.kaleido.io/blockchain-platform/quorum>

¹⁵ <https://eosnetwork.com/>

¹⁶ <https://www.avax.network/>

digital contracting, allowing for **automated and trust-free execution of agreements** within a decentralized framework. Essentially, smart contracts act as **programmable scripts that automatically enforce and carry out the contract terms** once specific conditions are fulfilled.

Smart contracts leverage the concept of decentralization, meaning they execute across all nodes in the network to ensure consensus and trust without relying on intermediaries. This decentralized execution guarantees that contract actions are immutable and transparent, as every action is recorded on the Blockchain ledger, allowing verification by any network participant.

An important feature of smart contracts is their capability to automate processes and enforce predetermined rules without human involvement. This automation minimizes the risk of human error, speeds up transaction processing, and boosts operational efficiency. By embedding business logic directly into smart contracts, organizations can streamline various processes, including asset transfers, supply chain management and regulatory compliance.

Smart contracts function according to a series of predefined conditions known as triggers. These triggers dictate the situations under which the contract will carry out specific actions. For instance, within a supply chain management context, a smart contract might automatically disburse payment to a supplier once it verifies that a shipment has been received.

A key application of smart contracts is security auditing, which aims to enhance the overall security of the Blockchain Infrastructure by leveraging auditing processes during the development of the smart contracts' logic. These contracts are carefully crafted to comply with security protocols and industry standards [5]. By integrating security measures directly into their code, smart contracts reduce the risks of fraud, tampering, and unauthorized access, thus bolstering the security of the digital infrastructure. Beyond security auditing, smart contracts enable data exchange, policy enforcement and access management. Authorized users can interact with these contracts via public interfaces on Blockchain, initiating contract execution and documenting outcomes on an immutable ledger. This process ensures transparency, accountability, and trust among all network participants.

Despite the many advantages of smart contracts, it is imperative to recognize the potential risks and challenges that come with their implementation. Issues like re-entrancy attacks and front-running exploits need careful attention and effective mitigation strategies. Additionally, the complexity involved in developing smart contracts and the necessity for thorough testing and auditing demand specialized skills and expertise.

2.2.3 Consensus Algorithms

In Blockchain technology, one of the key challenges is achieving consensus across a decentralized network of nodes. A consensus in a Blockchain network is a mechanism used to achieve **agreement on the state of the ledger among distributed Blockchain nodes**. It ensures that all nodes agree on the same version of the Blockchain, which is crucial for maintaining its integrity and security. Nodes need to collectively validate transactions while accounting for potential malicious actors. To overcome this challenge, several consensus algorithms have been introduced [6].

- **Proof of Work (PoW)** is the foundational consensus mechanism for Bitcoin. It requires miners to solve complex cryptographic puzzles to validate and add new blocks to the Blockchain. Although PoW provides strong security against double-spending attacks, it is highly resource-intensive and vulnerable to 51% attacks (i.e. malicious control of more than 50% of the Blockchain nodes), making it less energy-efficient.

- **Proof of Stake (PoS)** provides a more energy-efficient and 51% attack-resistant alternative to Proof of Work. In PoS, participants stake a portion of their cryptocurrency as collateral to become validators, and they are chosen to create new blocks based on the amount they have staked. Although PoS has these benefits, it also poses the risk of centralizing wealth among participants, as specific nodes may concentrate most of the mining power and thus minimize trust in the Blockchain network.
- **Delegated Proof of Stake (DPoS)** enhances the PoS model by implementing a voting system where stakeholders elect delegates to validate transactions and produce blocks. DPoS addresses some PoS vulnerabilities, like the nothing-at-stake issue, but it also introduces centralization risks due to the concentration of power among the chosen delegates.
- **Proof of Capacity (PoC)** leverages available hard drive space for mining and validating transactions. Although PoC is efficient, it is vulnerable to malware attacks and limited by the amount of hard drive space.
- **Practical Byzantine Fault Tolerance (PBFT)** achieves consensus among a subset of nodes even when Byzantine faults occur. PBFT works by electing a leader to propose blocks, which are then validated by other nodes through several rounds of communication. This method improves throughput but relies on a predefined set of participants.
- **Proof of Authority (PoA)** depends on trusted nodes to validate transactions and blocks, eliminating the need for extensive computational resources. However, PoA raises centralization concerns because the network's security depends on a small number of trusted validators.
- **Proof of Elapsed Time (PoET)** uses a countdown mechanism to introduce randomness, selecting nodes with the shortest waiting period as block creators. Although PoET promotes decentralization and has low resource consumption, its dependence on trusted hardware restricts its suitability for public networks.
- **Raft**, inspired by Paxos, uses a leader-driven approach to maintain consensus. With its lightweight leader election process and crash fault tolerance, Raft facilitates high performance and correctness in distributed environments, enabling integrity and reliability in transactions and data management.

2.2.4 Identity Management & Access Control Mechanisms

Identity management and access policies are crucial in a Blockchain network to ensure **secure and authorized interactions among entities**. Effective identity management is necessary to verify the identities of the users in a secure manner, enhancing trust within the network. Access policies are also imperative to ensure that users can only access data they are authorized to, preventing unauthorized access and potential breaches in the Blockchain ledgers.

In ENTRUST, an innovative identity management (IDM) system that aspires to leverage Attribute-Based Access Control (ABAC) mechanisms with Self-Sovereign Identity (SSI) capabilities within the Blockchain framework, addressing stringent security requirements and granting data control to the data subjects is envisaged. In addition, ENTRUST's approach aims to transition from centralized identity management to a decentralized model, leveraging novel Verifiable Credentials (VCs) and Verifiable Presentations (VPs). VCs are cryptographically secure elements about an individual's attributes, while VPs allow individuals to selectively disclose information, as a subset of the Verifiable Credentials. This combination supports a decentralized identity ecosystem, moving away from centralized databases prone to breaches and misuse. In addition, ENTRUST

targets utilizing ABAC capabilities that enable dynamic and flexible access control based on attributes, enhancing security by considering multiple factors such as roles, context, and data sensitivity. By integrating ABAC with SSI on the Blockchain network, we empower data subjects to manage their identities and control access to their data autonomously. This convergence creates a robust framework where data subjects have the authority to grant or revoke access based on specific attributes and conditions, ensuring privacy and security.

In this hybrid model, we introduce an **orthogonal solution that will also seek to encapsulate eIDAS** (Electronic Identification, Authentication, and Trust Services) capabilities. eIDAS provides a regulatory framework for secure electronic interactions across the EU, ensuring legal validity and trust. By incorporating eIDAS capabilities, our system not only adheres to strict security standards but also enhances interoperability and compliance with regulatory requirements.

The ENTRUST project's identity management solution is particularly pertinent for applications in the medical device sector. Medical devices often handle sensitive patient data and require stringent security measures. Our approach ensures that medical devices have control over their trust-related information, with the ability to manage access based on verifiable attributes and conditions. This ensures that only authorized entities can access medical device data, maintaining privacy and security while supporting efficient healthcare delivery. In general, ENTRUST is **pioneering the design and development of a federated IDM system that will exploit the features of the SSI model and leverage the ABAC advancements** for safeguarding the access control functionalities in ENTRUST for the secure management of medical devices.

2.2.5 Privacy-Preserving Data Sharing

In the medical domain, privacy-preserving data sharing is crucial to ensure the confidentiality and security of the operational data generated by medical devices, while complying with regulatory frameworks such as the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). The ENTRUST project addresses this challenge by introducing a novel framework that enables **secure, transparent and accountable data sharing, strictly adhering to GDPR guidelines**.

Medical devices generate and handle considerable amounts of sensitive data, including device usage data and trust-related operational metrics, such as attestation data and verifiable attributes. Ensuring the privacy and security of such data while facilitating their necessary exchange is a critical concern. Privacy-preserving data sharing mechanisms are designed to allow data to be shared between medical devices and healthcare organizations without compromising the identity of the data owner.

At the core of the ENTRUST data strategy lies the integration of Blockchain technology to guarantee data provenance. The intrinsic immutability of the Blockchain ensures that once data is recorded, it remains unaltered, serving as a definitive source of truth. By storing data on the Blockchain, ENTRUST establishes an unchangeable record, fostering trust and transparency within the system, by providing a transparent and tamper-proof audit trail for data. This also aligns with GDPR's requirements for data integrity and accuracy.

To avoid storing large datasets on the Blockchain and in this sense reduce costs that would arise from the on-chain storage, ENTRUST envisages an insightful approach where only data pointers are stored on the Blockchain. Such pointers function as immutable references to the actual data's storage location. By storing only these references, the amount of data placed on the Blockchain is minimized, and the associated costs are also reduced. The indices act as verifiable links, allowing any participant in the Blockchain network to locate and verify the integrity of the off-chain data. This approach ensures compliance with GDPR's principle of data minimization by only storing essential information on-chain and keeping detailed data off-chain.

In this context, a significant amount of the data in ENTRUST is managed off-chain using scalable storage solutions such as Elasticsearch. Elasticsearch is a distributed, search and analytics engine capable of handling large volumes of unstructured data, offering the scalability needed for extensive projects like ENTRUST. By storing the actual data off-chain, ENTRUST benefits from lower costs and greater flexibility provided by distributed storage systems.

2.3 Selection of ENTRUST BC technology

In selecting the most suitable Blockchain platform for the ENTRUST Blockchain Infrastructure, we opted for **Hyperledger Fabric** over other Blockchain technologies due to its unique features and capabilities that **align perfectly with our requirements, particularly in the realm of trust management and granular access control**.

Hyperledger Fabric stands out for its permissioned architecture, which is specifically designed to support enterprise-level applications requiring a high degree of privacy and confidentiality. Unlike public Blockchains such as Bitcoin and Ethereum, which allow unrestricted access, Hyperledger Fabric offers a modular architecture that facilitates the implementation of sophisticated access control policies, which is crucial for the ENTRUST framework.

One of the core strengths of Hyperledger Fabric is its comprehensive support for Attribute-Based Access Control (ABAC) mechanisms. These granular access control capabilities ensure that only authenticated and authorized entities can access or manipulate data, thereby maintaining the integrity and confidentiality of sensitive information. The inherent agile access control mechanisms of Hyperledger Fabric will be combined with the ABAC capabilities to provide a solid authentication and authorization approach in the ENTRUST framework. This level of control is vital for managing the diverse and dynamic trust requirements in ENTRUST, where data integrity and privacy are paramount.

Hyperledger Fabric employs a Membership Service Provider (MSP) to manage identities across the network. The MSP allows the implementation of fine-grained access policies, enabling precise control over who can participate in the network, access specific data, or perform particular actions. This capability is essential in ENTRUST, where different entities may have varying levels of access, based on their Verifiable Presentations that constitute a set of attributes that follow the ENTRUST entities, such as medical devices, throughout their operations in the ENTRUST framework and designate which channels they are authorized to access in the ENTRUST DLT.

Additionally, Hyperledger Fabric supports private channels, which allow a subset of network participants to create a private ledger for conducting confidential transactions. This feature is particularly advantageous for ENTRUST, where certain transactions or data exchanges must remain confidential and only be accessible to specific parties. Private channels ensure that sensitive information is not exposed to the entire network, thus enhancing privacy and security.

The chaincode (smart contract logic) architecture of Hyperledger Fabric further enhances its flexibility and security. Chaincode in Fabric can enforce access controls at a granular level, ensuring that only authorized entities can execute certain operations or access specific datasets. This is crucial for maintaining the trustworthiness of the ENTRUST framework, as it prevents unauthorized manipulation of trust models and attestation evidence.

Moreover, Hyperledger Fabric's modular design allows the integration of customized consensus mechanisms that align with the specific security and performance needs of ENTRUST. This flexibility ensures that the platform can efficiently handle the diverse trust management and transaction processing requirements, supporting the scalability and robustness of the system.

Hyperledger Fabric also provides the capability for connection with trusted computing technologies that can further enhance the secure management of medical devices in ENTRUST. Additionally, Hyperledger Fabric can be connected to secure oracles through an already defined interface, unlike Besu, offering further options for secure and reliable data transactions in the ENTRUST Blockchain.

Hyperledger Fabric provides a secure and flexible framework for managing trust and ensuring data integrity. Its permissioned architecture, support for private channels, and modular design make it the ideal Blockchain platform to meet the stringent privacy, security, and trust management needs of the ENTRUST framework.

An overview of the comparison of the main candidate Blockchain technologies for ENTRUST Blockchain Infrastructure, based on security, integrity and performance criteria, is presented in the following Table 1, where the strengths of Hyperledger Fabric compared to the other candidate platforms is presented.

Table 1: Blockchain Platforms comparison

Blockchain Platform	Consensus Flexibility	Smart Contracts	Privacy	Transaction Speed	Access Control	Trusted Computing Compatibility
Ethereum	Medium	Yes	Low	High	Low	Low
Hyperledger Fabric	High	Yes	High	High	High	High
IOTA	Low	Yes	Low	High	Low	Low
Hyperledger Besu	High	Yes	High	Medium	Medium	Medium
Corda	High	Yes	High	Medium	Medium	Low
Quorum	High	Yes	High	Medium	Medium	Low

2.4 Summary of ENTRUST’s Ambition

ENTRUST aims to develop a comprehensive framework for ensuring the **security, privacy and operational assurance of Connected Medical Devices (CMDs) within healthcare organizations**. By integrating Blockchain technology, ENTRUST introduces several innovative solutions that significantly enhance trust management. These innovations address key challenges in the healthcare sector, providing a robust foundation for managing CMDs securely and transparently. Through these advancements, ENTRUST aspires to set a new standard for medical device cybersecurity and trust management, driving forward the state-of-the-art in the healthcare industry. Also, the decentralized nature of Blockchain eliminates the need for a central authority to manage and verify trust. Instead, trust is established through consensus mechanisms and distributed nodes. Such decentralization reduces the Single Points of Failure by distributing trust verification across multiple nodes, boosting the reliability and robustness of trust management. In addition, the decentralized verification of the Blockchain makes it more challenging for malicious entities to compromise the system, thereby enhancing the overall security of CMD management.

The core reasons behind leveraging the Blockchain technology in the context of ENTRUST are (a) for the **auditability and integrity of all the data-related transactions and flows** needed to support ENTRUST’s trust assessment process, (b) for supporting the **enforcement of trust policies in an auditable and verifiable manner** and (c) for **efficient and scalable certifiability**

of the medical devices through the usage of Conformity Certificates (CC) assisted by the privacy-preserving threat intelligence sharing.

Blockchain technology due to its inherent immutable characteristic, ensures that every data transaction related to CMDs is permanently recorded and cannot be modified or deleted by any entity. This is crucial for trust management as every action and update regarding CMDs is logged, creating a reliable history that stakeholders can trust, while the permanent records in the Blockchain facilitate comprehensive tracking of CMDs throughout their lifecycle, enhancing accountability and transparency. More specifically, ENTRUST's Blockchain supports the data lifecycle management of CMDs, including all the necessary data-related flows. By storing data on the immutable ledger its integrity is guaranteed providing at the same time a means to audit what and when is stored on the ledger.

On top of that, ENTRUST's Blockchain infrastructure supports the enforcement of trust policies in an auditable and verifiable manner. Thus, Blockchain technology enhances integrity monitoring of all of the processes that are part of this security/trust policy, while none can repudiate the enforcement of these policies. At the same time, ENTRUST's private channel is assuring that only authorized user/entities can either push or retrieve sensitive data to/from the ledger. These advanced access control capabilities enable granular management of who can access data related to CMDs. The granular access control helps healthcare organizations comply with strict regulatory requirements by ensuring that data access is precisely managed and monitored.

Another core ENTRUST innovation is the certifiability of CMDs leveraging the CC as a proof of certified device. Such information is stored on the public channel of ENTRUST Blockchain infrastructure in order for any ENTRUST component or external auditor to be in position to verify whether the CMD is certified or not. Moreover, this feature is further supported by the ENTRUST Hygiene Marketplace, another public channel of ENTRUST, to share information in STIX format about the new identified threat and vulnerabilities in a privacy preserving manner to avoid fingerprinting. To establish and share threat intelligence information to enable a more efficient and scalable certifiability of the devices based on the updated protection profiles of the manufacturer is of paramount importance. In the context of ENTRUST, STIX format is leveraged as a widely accepted standard that also omits sensitive information, a necessary feature in such a sensitive domain of medical devices. ENTRUST Hygiene Marketplace reinforces the certifiability of CMDs since it provides an easy reaction on a potential threat/vulnerability even when these have not been materialized yet in the specific domain.

3 ENTRUST Blockchain and Tracer Data Workflows and Relevant Requirements

This chapter describes thoroughly both the Blockchain and Tracer related data types (e.g., attestation data, application data, Trust Policy, Conformity Certificates and Domain-level eMUD), formats (e.g., compliance with standards such as GDPR and FHIR), behaviors, workflows and its corresponding requirements (e.g., general and security requirements).

3.1 Types of Data Considered in ENTRUST Blockchain and Tracing

A wide variety of data types is leveraged within the ENTRUST Blockchain towards safeguarding the secure management of medical devices in the ENTRUST framework. A critical type of data stored in the ENTRUST Blockchain is the **attestation data** (attestation reports and raw attestation traces) generated from a medical device's attestation process. The attestation traces are stored in the Off-Chain Storage (see also section 0) due to their large size to facilitate the performance of the ENTRUST Blockchain. The attestation data are subsequently used for the recalculation of the actual trust level of a device and the update of the trust policies for the device and the domain by the TAF, when the required level of trust for the device is higher than the actual level. Another important data type is the **Trust Policy** which is stored in the Private Ledger of the ENTRUST Blockchain Infrastructure and constitutes the benchmark for the measurement of the trustworthiness level of the medical devices in the ENTRUST framework.

In addition, **application data**, including network logs, are stored in the ENTRUST Blockchain when a medical device generates a tracing process for monitoring its system behavior within the context of a specific application. Moreover, **Conformity Certificates** (CC) reside in the Public Ledger of the ENTRUST Blockchain, which are created by the TAF after the evaluation of the trust level of a medical device or the domain from a third-party auditor. Another data type that is stored in the Public Ledger is the **Domain-level eMUDs** which are generated during the domain enrollment phase by the Domain Manager and contain the collective list of threats for the devices of the domain. Furthermore, the **VCs** and **VPs** that are created by the Privacy CA and the high-end medical devices respectively, are used within the ENTRUST Blockchain for the authorization of medical devices to get access to the Blockchain.

In the ENTRUST framework, a comprehensive approach to data collection is essential for ensuring the security and trustworthiness of CMDs. The types of data considered in ENTRUST tracing include both static and runtime properties, which together provide a holistic view of the device's operational integrity. **Static properties** encompass data such as the secure boot sequence, which verifies the integrity and authenticity of the firmware before execution, ensuring that only trusted software runs on the device. **Runtime properties** include critical performance metrics like CPU usage, memory utilization, and system call activities, which are monitored in real-time to detect anomalies, performance bottlenecks, and potential security breaches. Additionally, detailed **logs of events** captured during the device's operation, including task execution and interrupt handling, provide granular insights into the system's behavior. **Network monitoring data**, such as TCP/IP connections and packet transmissions, help in identifying unauthorized network activities, while filesystem and database monitoring track file operations and database queries, ensuring data integrity and preventing unauthorized access. By integrating these diverse types of data, the ENTRUST tracer supports robust trust assessment, AI-based anomaly detection, and real-time security management, thereby maintaining the reliability and safety of CMDs.

3.2 ENTRUST Blockchain and Tracing Data Sharing Behaviors & Workflows

ENTRUST leverages the capabilities of Blockchain towards setting up dedicated data sharing behaviors and workflows that safeguard the secure management of medical devices. Different specific types of data sharing workflows are envisaged, as summarized in the Table 2 below. Detailed information about each data sharing workflow is presented in section 1.1.

Table 2: Data sharing workflows

Data Sharing Workflow	Description
Trust policy	This workflow refers to the trust assessment process that is run by the Risk Assessment Engine and the TAF and results in the generation of the trust policy for the device and the generation/amendment of the trust policy for the domain. The trust policies are recorded in the Private Ledger of the ENTRUST DLT through smart contracts.
Attestation data	This workflow pertains to the attestation process that is initiated by a medical device (verifier) and generates an attestation report and attestation raw data regarding the trust level of a device (prover). The attestation report is stored in the Private Ledger and the attestation raw data in the Off-Chain Storage, while a storage location pointer is also stored in the Private Ledger, through smart contracts to ensure integrity and confidentiality.
Application data	This workflow pertains to the generation of application data including network logs by a medical device towards monitoring its behavior under the context of a certain application. These data are collected by the Tracer during attestation and consumed by the Digital Twins for detecting potential threats through an attack emulation process, while they are recorded through smart contracts to the Private Ledger for auditability purposes.
Conformity Certificates	This workflow refers to the trustworthiness check initiated by a third-party auditor regarding a device or the domain either in a regular manner or randomly due to a new policy. The Conformity Certificate of the device/domain is revoked from the Public Ledger if $ATL < RTL$ after a check by TAF, or else it is created and stored in the Public Ledger.
Domain-level eMUDs	This workflow refers to the domain enrolment phase where after the trust assessment process and the definition of trust policies and RTLs, the Domain-level eMUD is generated as an extension of the eMUDs of the devices of the domain. The Domain-level eMUD is stored in the Public Ledger through a smart contract, containing information about the collective list of threats, the RTLs and key restriction usage policies for the devices in the domain.

3.3 Data Lifecycle Management

The ENTRUST project is focused on the secure management of medical devices, leveraging Blockchain technology to ensure robust data security and compliance with both FHIR and GDPR standards. The data lifecycle within the ENTRUST Blockchain encompasses several key features designed to enhance security, data protection, and interoperability.

In ENTRUST, secure communication of medical data is imperative. Utilizing FHIR standards, ENTRUST ensures interoperability between medical devices and healthcare domains. This is

achieved through standardized data formats such as JSON, which facilitate seamless data sharing while maintaining high security standards. A significant amount of sensitive data (e.g., attestation evidence) transmitted within the ENTRUST network is encrypted using ABE cryptographic protocols, ensuring that sensitive medical information is protected during data transactions. Access control mechanisms leveraging ABAC and VCs and VPs are also utilized for safeguarding the secure access of ENTRUST entities to the medical information stored in the Blockchain.

ENTRUST aims to take strict data protection measures in accordance with GDPR and FHIR requirements. GDPR mandates that personal data be processed lawfully, transparently, and for a specified purpose. ENTRUST adheres to these principles by implementing a trustworthiness framework that calculates and monitors the trust level of medical devices in a specific domain towards addressing any threat or vulnerability that may expose sensitive medical information, ensuring compliance with GDPR's transparency and accountability provisions. Furthermore, FHIR's privacy and security guidelines are integrated into the ENTRUST system, ensuring that patient data remains confidential and secure, as the trustworthiness of medical devices is continuously checked.

Moreover, to ensure compliance with GDPR and FHIR, ENTRUST employs various cryptographic primitives. These include encryption algorithms to secure data at rest and in transit, digital signatures to verify the authenticity of data, and hashing techniques to maintain data integrity. These cryptographic measures prevent unauthorized access and modifications, ensuring that medical data are handled securely and in accordance with regulatory standards. More information about these crypto primitives is presented in deliverable D4.2 [7].

Blockchain technology is integral to ENTRUST, providing a transparent and immutable ledger for data provenance and auditability. Each transaction involving medical device data is recorded on the Blockchain, creating a verifiable audit trail. This ensures that the history of the data can be traced from its origin to its current state, enhancing accountability and transparency. The decentralized nature of Blockchain also reduces the risk of data tampering, as all changes are recorded and cannot be modified without consensus from the network.

In addition, ENTRUST enhances data integrity through the use of Attribute-Based Signatures (ABS). ABS allows for fine-grained access control and verification, ensuring that only authorized individuals can sign and access specific data attributes. This mechanism verifies the data's authenticity and ensures that any changes are made by authorized entities, such as Domain Managers and Security Administrators, maintaining the integrity and trustworthiness of the medical data. By combining ABS with Blockchain, ENTRUST provides a robust framework for securing medical device data throughout its lifecycle.

3.3.1 Data Format

Within the ENTRUST Blockchain, the need for data interoperability brings in the definition of the necessary data formats. Since Hyperledger Fabric is utilized as the Blockchain technology in ENTRUST to ensure data integrity, security and provenance, JSON data format is used due to its interoperable and standardized text-based structure, enabling seamless data sharing between ENTRUST entities. For the design and execution of smart contracts in ENTRUST Blockchain Infrastructure, the Solidity language will be used, thus making JSON data format an excellent choice for smooth transaction flows. The JSON data format will be used for all different types of data that will be leveraged in ENTRUST Blockchain such as application data, attestation data and trust policies.

Regarding the Tracer, the following Tables provide a comprehensive overview of the various monitoring and data collection mechanisms employed within the ENTRUST framework. These mechanisms are crucial for ensuring the performance, security, and integrity of CMDs. Each table categorizes different types of monitoring methods, attributes, and their corresponding units of measurement, highlighting how they contribute to the overall trust assessment and anomaly detection processes. By systematically capturing and analysing detailed logs and performance metrics, the tracer supports real-time monitoring, security auditing, and operational optimization, thereby maintaining the trustworthiness and reliability of CMDs. The tables below are organized into categories such as Performance Monitoring, Security Monitoring, Network Monitoring, Filesystem Monitoring, Database Monitoring, System Calls and Kernel Monitoring, Detailed Logs of Events Captured, Summary of Thread and Context Execution Details, and Secure Boot, each describing specific tracking methods and their respective units of measurement.

Table 3: Performance Monitoring

Tracking Method	Format
biolateny-bpfcc	Latency (milliseconds)
biotop-bpfcc	I/O operations per process
biosnoop-bpfcc	Detailed trace of I/O operations
cpudist-bpfcc	CPU time distribution (percentage)
execsnoop-bpfcc	Process execution logs
funccount-bpfcc	Function call counts
funclateny-bpfcc	Function call latency (milliseconds)
offcputime-bpfcc	Off-CPU time (milliseconds)
runqlat-bpfcc	Scheduler run queue latency (milliseconds)

Table 4: Security Monitoring

Tracking Method	Format
capable-bpfcc	Capability check logs
execsnoop-bpfcc	Process execution logs
killsnoop-bpfcc	Signal sending logs
opensnoop-bpfcc	File access logs
bindsnoop-bpfcc	Network address/port bindings
Secure Boot	Signature hash

Table 5: Network Monitoring

Tracking Method	Format
tcpconnect-bpfcc	Active TCP connections
tcpaccept-bpfcc	Passive TCP connections
tcplife-bpfcc	TCP connection lifespan (seconds)

tcpretrans-bpfcc	TCP retransmits
netqtop-bpfcc	Network traffic statistics

Table 6: Filesystem Monitoring

Tracking Method	Format
filelife-bpfcc	File creation/deletion logs
fileslower-bpfcc	File operation latency (milliseconds)
ext4dist-bpfcc	Ext4 operation latencies (milliseconds)
btrfsdist-bpfcc	Btrfs operation latencies (milliseconds)

Table 7: Database Monitoring

Tracking Method	Format
dbslower-bpfcc	Slow database queries (milliseconds)
dbstat-bpfcc	Database operation statistics

Table 8: System Calls and Kernel Monitoring

Tracking Method	Format
argdist-bpfcc	Function argument values
biosnoop-bpfcc	Block I/O requests
cachestat-bpfcc	Cache hit/miss ratios
cachetop-bpfcc	Top cache users
funccount-bpfcc	Function call counts
funcslower-bpfcc	Slow kernel functions (milliseconds)

Table 9: Detailed Logs of Events Captured

Tracking Method	Format
Sequencenum	Sequential number
Timestamp	Time (seconds nanoseconds)
Context	System state
Event	Event type
Detail	Additional event details
Timestampint	Integer timestamp
Contextinint	Integer input context
Contextint	Integer current context
Contextoutint	Integer output context

Eventint	Integer event code
Eventoffset	Event log offset
Eventsize	Event data size
Eventdata	Raw event data

Table 10: Thread and Context Execution Details

Tracking Method	Format
Name	Thread/context name
Type	Context type identifier
Stack Information	Stack size and memory address
Activations	Number of activations
Total Blocked Time	Time blocked (milliseconds)
Total Run Time	Run time (milliseconds)
Time Interrupted	Time interrupted (milliseconds)
CPU Load	CPU load (percentage)
Last Run Time	Last run time (milliseconds)
Min Run Time	Minimum run time (milliseconds)
Max Run Time	Maximum run time (milliseconds)
Min Blocked Time	Minimum blocked time (milliseconds)
Max Blocked Time	Maximum blocked time (milliseconds)
Run Time/s	Run time per second (milliseconds)
Min Run Time/s	Minimum run time per second (milliseconds)
Max Run Time/s	Maximum run time per second (milliseconds)

3.4 Privacy, Security and Trust Requirements

Within the ENTRUST framework, a series of different requirements regarding privacy, security and trust are emerging, towards safeguarding the secure management of medical devices in the healthcare domain. In the following subchapters, the requirements that embrace the Blockchain and the Tracer are described.

3.4.1 Blockchain Requirements

The ENTRUST Blockchain serves as the necessary technological component that ensures data provenance, integrity and security in the ENTRUST framework. Specific dedicated requirements are necessary towards defining the optimal operation of the Blockchain in order to enable the secure management of medical devices. In this section, a set of general requirements for the ENTRUST Blockchain is first presented, while subsequently requirements about specific aspects such as data confidentiality and integrity, authorization and access control, data encryption, data trustworthiness and accountability are specified.

Table 11: ENTRUST DLT General Requirements

Requirement	Description	Status
DLT01-Data Confidentiality and Integrity	Data stored in the ENTRUST DLT shall maintain confidentiality and integrity to prohibit unauthorized access and foster trust among all data transactions. In this context, the attestation raw data shall be encrypted with ABE and signed with ABS.	Mandatory
DLT02-Data Sharing	All data sharing flows leveraging the ENTRUST Blockchain, such as workflows regarding attestation data and application data, shall be safeguarded, so that information is exchanged among ENTRUST entities in a secure manner.	Mandatory
DLT03-Authorization and Access Control	Access to data stored in the ENTRUST Blockchain shall be safeguarded by applying a 2-round authorization process for the devices, encapsulating the check of certificates as issued by the Blockchain CA and the check of VPs by the ABAC component. Smart contracts shall seal such transactions by using such verifiable attributes.	Mandatory
DLT04-Device and Domain Privacy	Dedicated measures shall be employed by the ENTRUST DLT for safeguarding the privacy of device data based on GDPR, FHIR and other medical-related standards and regulations.	Mandatory
DLT05-Forward and Backward Privacy	Forward and backward privacy measures shall be developed within ENTRUST DLT to block past and future exposure of device data because of identity or key compromises.	Desirable
DLT06-Data Encryption	Attribute-based Encryption (ABE) mechanisms shall be leveraged in the ENTRUST DLT so that data stored in the Off-Chain Storage remain secure and get accessed only by authorized entities.	Mandatory
DLT07-Data Trustworthiness	The ENTRUST entities that exchange data with the ENTRUST DLT shall be verified through certificates and Verifiable Presentations to ensure their trustworthiness.	Mandatory
DLT08-Entity Authentication	The ENTRUST entities shall be authenticated in the ENTRUST DLT in order to participate in secure data sharing workflows.	Mandatory
DLT09-Non-repudiation and Accountability	The data transactions that are recorded in the ENTRUST DLT shall be immutable to ensure traceability and accountability of transactions in ENTRUST framework.	Mandatory
DLT10-Ledgers Security	The security of the Private and Public Ledgers of the ENTRUST DLT shall be safeguarded by allowing access only to authorized entities in order to assure the integrity and confidentiality of stored data.	Mandatory
DLT11-Secure Data Lifecycle Management	Device data shall be maintained secure within their entire lifecycle in order to ensure data protection in ENTRUST DLT.	Mandatory

DLT12-Data Interoperability	An API Layer shall be employed in the ENTRUST DLT for transformation of data exchanged among entities in a format that is readable for the deployment of the smart contracts.	Mandatory
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Table 12: ENTRUST DLT Data Confidentiality and Integrity Requirements

<i>SEC1 Data Confidentiality and Integrity</i> <i>The data in ENTRUST DLT shall be safeguarded through necessary measurements towards ensuring their integrity, confidentiality, and availability during the entire data lifecycle.</i>		
Requirement	Description	Status
DLT-DCI-01	The ENTRUST DLT shall be deployed with sufficient number of Blockchain Peers to ensure data integrity in the Ledgers.	Mandatory
DLT-DCI-02	The consensus mechanism of ENTRUST Blockchain shall safeguard the data integrity in the Ledgers.	Mandatory
DLT-DCI-03	The ENTRUST DLT shall provide an Off-Chain Storage to ensure the availability of sensitive and large-size data, such as attestation-related evidence.	Mandatory
DLT-DCI-04	Smart contracts shall be utilised in the ENTRUST DLT for the secure recording of data transactions in the ENTRUST framework.	Mandatory
DLT-DCI-05	Confidentiality of data stored in the ledgers shall be ensured by leveraging encryption mechanisms.	Mandatory
DLT-DCI-06	The storage location pointers that will reside in the Private Ledgers shall be encrypted to further ensure the integrity of the actual data that they point into at the Off-Chain Storage.	Mandatory
DLT-DCI-07	The entities in the ENTRUST Framework shall not be able to access the Off-Chain Storage without prior communication with the Security Context Broker.	Mandatory
DLT-DCI-08	The CMDs shall carry their authentication attributes (Verifiable Presentations) in their wallets.	Mandatory
DLT-DCI-09	The Security Context Broker and the ENTRUST DLT shall exchange information in a secure manner.	Mandatory
DLT-DCI-10	Sensitive and/or large-size data shall be maintained in the Off-Chain Storage of ENTRUST DLT for security and performance purposes (e.g., large-size attestation raw data).	Mandatory
DLT-DCI-11	The storage location of data in the Off-chain Storage shall be maintained as pointers in the Private Ledger of the ENTRUST DLT.	Mandatory
DLT-DCI-12	The ENTRUST DLT shall consist of different private channels, each of them belonging to a different ENTRUST Use Case domain (e.g., hospital), towards ensuring the security of information exchanged among medical devices in a specific domain.	Mandatory

DLT-DCI-13	The ENTRUST DLT shall employ a public channel to enable the storage of conformity certificates of medical devices that can be leveraged for auditability purposes.	Mandatory
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Table 13: ENTRUST DLT Authorisation and Access Control Requirements

SEC2 Authorisation and Access Control The entities in the ENTRUST framework shall have access to the ENTRUST DLT according to specific attribute-based access policies, leveraging the authorisation and authentication mechanisms of ENTRUST DLT.		
Requirement	Description	Status
DLT-AAC-01	The access policies to the channels of the ENTRUST DLT shall be governed by the Domain Managers and Security Administrators of ENTRUST framework.	Mandatory
DLT-AAC-02	The access policies that govern the data transactions in the ENTRUST DLT shall be encapsulated in the deployed smart contracts.	Mandatory
DLT-AAC-03	The authentication and access control mechanisms in ENTRUST DLT shall be leveraged by the ABAC Service and the Security Context Broker.	Mandatory
DLT-AAC-04	The data stored in the ENTRUST DLT shall be accessed only by entities that possess the necessary attributes, leveraging their Verifiable Presentations that prove the ownership of a specific set of such attributes.	Mandatory
DLT-AAC-05	The ENTRUST DLT shall employ a Blockchain CA to issue credentials to the entities for accessing the DLT.	Mandatory

Table 14: ENTRUST DLT Data Encryption Requirements

SEC3 Data Encryption Data in the Off-Chain Storage and storage pointers in the Private Ledger of the ENTRUST DLT shall be encrypted through Attribute-Based Encryption (ABE) mechanisms to assure data privacy and security.		
Requirement	Description	Status
DLT-ENC-01	The ABE mechanisms in ENTRUST DLT shall enable the encryption of data both in the Private Ledger (for storage location pointers into Off-Chain Storage) and in the Off-Chain Storage (for the actual sensitive or large-size data) by leveraging the appropriate attributes per case.	Mandatory
DLT-ENC-02	ABE mechanisms shall be exploited in the ENTRUST DLT and only entities that possess the required attributes will be able to decrypt the encrypted data.	Mandatory

Table 15: ENTRUST DLT Data Trustworthiness Requirements

SEC4 Data Trustworthiness ENTRUST DLT shall enable the storage of trust policies in the Private Ledgers that will be utilised for the trust management of CMDs in the ENTRUST framework.		
Requirement	Description	Status

DLT-DT-01	The ENTRUST DLT shall enable access, based on necessary Verifiable Presentations, to the entities that want to perform calculation of the trustworthiness level of CMDs in the ENTRUST framework.	Mandatory
DLT-DT-02	The Privacy CA of the ENTRUST DLT shall be leveraged for the management and verification of credentials of CMDs in the ENTRUST framework.	Mandatory
DLT-DT-03	Attestation reports, trust policies, protection profiles (extended MUDs), conformity certificates and application data for misbehaviour detection shall be deployed as smart contracts into the ENTRUST DLT to ensure the trust management in the ENTRUST framework.	Mandatory

Table 16: ENTRUST DLT Non-repudiation and Accountability Requirements

<i>SEC5 Non-repudiation and Accountability of Actions</i> <i>The ENTRUST DLT shall ensure the accountability of all data transactions performed by the entities of the ENTRUST framework.</i>		
Requirement	Description	Status
DLT-NRA-01	The ENTRUST DLT shall not permit the deletion or update of data stored in the Ledgers.	Mandatory
DLT-NRA-02	The hashes of data transactions shall be stored in the Private Ledger to facilitate the traceability of transactions in the ENTRUST framework.	Mandatory
DLT-NRA-03	The validation of data transactions in the ENTRUST DLT shall be performed by a group of Blockchain Peers.	Mandatory
DLT-NRA-04	The resolutions of the majority of the Blockchain Peers shall be considered by the consensus mechanism of the ENTRUST DLT.	Mandatory

3.4.2 Tracer Requirements

The ENTRUST Tracer is a crucial component that ensures comprehensive system visibility and security for CMDs. Specific dedicated requirements are necessary to define the optimal operation of the tracer, enabling accurate and detailed monitoring while maintaining minimal impact on device performance. In this section, a set of general requirements for the ENTRUST Tracer is first presented, followed by specific requirements related to functionality and security, but depending on the type of device and hardware they are instantiated these requirements might have a different weight. These requirements encompass efficient hardware utilization, comprehensive access to device attributes, compatibility with various devices, data exportability, robust access control mechanisms, secure boot processes, and the use of cryptographic measures to ensure data integrity and authenticity.

Table 17: Tracer General Requirements

Requirement	Description	Status
TR-GEN-01	Efficient utilization of device's hardware resources to ensure minimal impact on performance while maintaining accurate and detailed monitoring.	Mandatory
TR-GEN-02	Comprehensive access to the core attributes and properties of the device, including CPU usage, memory utilization, and peripheral status.	Mandatory
TR-GEN-03	Compatibility with a wide range of devices and configurations, enabling seamless integration into diverse environments and systems.	Mandatory
TR-GEN-04	Data collected by the tracer should be easily interpretable and accessible, provided in a clear and structured format.	Mandatory

Table 18: Tracer Functional Requirements

Requirement	Description	Status
TR-FUNC-01	The tracer should provide detailed logs of events captured and summaries of thread and context execution details.	Mandatory
TR-FUNC-02	Data collected should be exportable in standard formats that can be easily analyzed using various tools and software.	Mandatory
TR-FUNC-03	Allow selective data sharing, ensuring that only relevant portions of the data are shared with AI anomaly detection systems and other authorized entities.	Desirable
TR-FUNC-04	Enable the use of digital signatures for log entries to ensure their authenticity. Each log entry should be signed using the device's private key.	Desirable
TR-FUNC-05	Ensure that medical devices use a secure boot process, which verifies the integrity and authenticity of the software before execution.	Mandatory

Table 19: Traces Security Requirements

Requirement	Description	Status
TR-SEC-01	The tracer must create cryptographic hashes of the logs and traces and record these hashes on the Blockchain.	Mandatory
TR-SEC-02	Implement robust access control mechanisms to ensure that only trusted entities, such as manufacturers and domain-authorized personnel, can access the stored data.	Mandatory
TR-SEC-03	All data transmitted between medical devices and external systems must be encrypted using strong encryption protocols.	Mandatory

TR-SEC-04	The data retrieval process must guarantee that the logs and traces remain tamper-proof and consistent with the original records, using Blockchain-anchored hash references.	Mandatory
TR-SEC-05	Ensure that medical devices use a secure boot process, which verifies the integrity and authenticity of the software before execution, preventing the device from running untrusted code.	Mandatory
TR-SEC-06	The tracer must utilize locality-based protection ¹⁷ , where the TPM enforces commands to be executed only by processes running in the secure world, ensuring that only trusted components interact with the TPM.	Mandatory

¹⁷ <https://www.snia.org/educational-library/tcg-dice-dmtf-spd-m-binding-overview-2022>

4 ENTRUST Blockchain Architecture & Functional Components

This chapter describes the ENTRUST Blockchain architecture and is the core chapter of the document. As already mentioned, ENTRUST's vision is to enhance the secure life-cycle management of CMDs from zero-touch on-boarding to operational assurance and data sharing in a secure and privacy-preserving manner. To support this vision, ENTRUST employs a Blockchain infrastructure which is responsible for various functionalities regarding data sharing and provenance/auditability functionalities. Both as it pertains to trustworthiness evidence but also for user data that need to adhere to strict privacy requirements. In addition, the Blockchain infrastructure is intended to store and manage security policy-related data and threat intelligence reports towards achieving certifiability as one important dimension of CMDs. Since several components synthesize the ENTRUST Blockchain infrastructure, the chapter aims to highlight how these components operate synergistically to meet ENTRUST's vision.

ENTRUST's Blockchain architecture is a mix of permissioned and public networks. This means that (a) allows access to **authenticated and authorized members to provide the highest level of security guarantees in such a sensitive domain** of medical systems as well as (b) **access to everyone interested in the public information of the infrastructure (e.g., Conformity Certificates and Threat Intelligence)**. Thus, the architecture supports **three different channels** to satisfy the different privacy requirements. Towards this direction, the ENTRUST architecture supports a **private channel** for storing all the sensitive information (e.g., trust policies, application-related data, and attestation-related data) for supporting the ENTRUST stakeholders, a **public channel** for storing the public information, such as Conformity Certificates (CC) and Domain-specific eMUD files per device enhanced with domain-specific identified threats/vulnerabilities, and a different public channel, namely **Hygiene Marketplace channel**, for storing and sharing the identified threat intelligence data with other stakeholders of the medical domain. The entire purpose of this "Hygiene Marketplace" is two-fold; (a) to allow the secure and privacy-preserving sharing of any threats identified, and (b) to apply the necessary filtering to avoid disclosing any sensitive information. It must be noted here that we also adopted the well-known Structured Threat Information eXpression (STIX) format for sharing this type of information as a standardized language for exchanging cyber threat intelligence in a privacy-preserving manner, since it omits the sensitive information.

ENTRUST's Blockchain infrastructure enhances the traceability and verifiability of ENTRUST processes in accordance with the requirements defined in Chapter 0. Also, for enhancing the Blockchain scalability, different nodes can be deployed capable to host the chaincode for supporting the on-chain interactions of these channels. It must be noted here that off-chain data storage is necessary for storing raw data (due to their inherent large size) in an encrypted format, while the corresponding storage pointers are amended on the chain. ENTRUST designs a novel, decentralized Attribute-based Encryption (ABE) mechanisms for safeguarding the integrity and confidentiality of the off-chain data enabling the process of only authorized entities (e.g., that can prove ownership of the appropriate set of attributes) can decrypt and access the data. On top of that, a **two-layered access control mechanism** for authorization in the HyperLedger Fabric Blockchain is employed, leveraging an ABAC and the HyperLedger Fabric's internal access control mechanism, the Membership Service Provider (MSP). This access control mechanism is an **innovation brought forth by ENTRUST towards achieving a more granular enforcement** of usage control policies directly on the chain.

In addition, the **Security Context Broker (SCB)** component of the architecture acts as an intermediate entity between the ENTRUST Blockchain network and the outside world by handling all the communication between the peers, the off-chain storage, and the access control-related requests of the rest of the architecture components. Thus, it is responsible for offering a bridge

between the Blockchain network and the outside world. The adoption of such component is a design choice that limits the decentralized nature of the Blockchain by positioning a centralized infrastructure entity for mediating the interactions with the off-chain data to limit the attack vector. On top of that it allows better control on data interactions, since all interactions are through this component. ENTRUST’s core Blockchain-related architectural components are summarized in the following table.

Table 20: Core Blockchain-related architectural components

Component	Description
ABAC	An additional Attribute-based Access Control mechanism for accessing specific data blobs on the chain. This functionality is part of all the smart contracts (e.g., read or store data)
ABE	An Attribute-based Encryption mechanism for storing safely data to the Off-Chain Data Storage.
Off-Chain Data Storage	The supporting off-chain storage that stores encrypted data.
MSP	Hyperledger Fabric’s internal access control mechanism for accessing blockchain channels, namely Membership Service Provider.
SCB	A secure centralized entity for interacting with the Blockchain infrastructure in order to minimize the attack vector in the sensitive domain of CMDs.

ENTRUST’s endmost goal is to support secure lifecycle management, thus in the context of this operational landscape, ENTRUST uses the Blockchain to equip the devices with the appropriate crypto primitives during onboarding to operate during runtime in a trustworthy manner (see 4.1.1 Flow 1: Preparing the Device for Trustworthiness Establishment), but also to establish (see 4.1.2 Flow 2: Establishing Device Trustworthiness) and re-establish trust (see 4.1.3 Flow 3: Re-establishing Device Trustworthiness). More details are provided in the following subsections that aim to take apart the overall architecture and describe the architectural flows among the components and their functional objective. The high-level overview of the ENTRUST Blockchain conceptual architecture, including the components, their interactions, and the different clients (e.g., high-end or low-end devices) is depicted in Figure 1 below. Different colours highlight these three flows, where red, pink and orange depict the Flow 1, blue, green and petrol depict the Flow 2 and dark purple the Flow 3. This is also pinpointed with more details in the legend of the Figure.

Figure 2 High-level ENTRUST Blockchain Architecture

4.1 High-level Architectural Flows

ENTRUST's conceptual Blockchain architecture can be grouped into **three separate flows for enabling the secure life-cycle management of CMDs** including the establishment of trustworthy CMD domains. Essentially, these flows are the implicit phases that enable the secure lifecycle management of CMDs. In order to **prepare the devices to establish their trust level**, we need to provide adequate guarantees that they will be equipped with the appropriate crypto primitives binding to the appropriate set of key restriction usage policies (as defined in the context of D4.2) so as to ensure their conformance to the expected behaviour defined in the corresponding eMUD profile (D3.2). In the same context, **enabling a device to establish their trust level** requires the monitoring and collection of trustworthiness evidence, during runtime, in a verifiable manner. The governing factor in this process is the trust policy comprising all information needed by the TAF for orchestrating this runtime trust assessment: Type of trust evidence that need to be monitored so that the Actual Trust Level can be calculated per device and subsequently to be securely elevated to the trustworthiness level of the entire CMD domain. Towards this direction, ENTRUST identified three core flows for establishing the secure lifecycle management of CMDs, from the moment it gets bootstrapped so as to be securely onboarded to a domain, equipped with the necessary crypto primitives, to its runtime operation and reaction to potential events enabling the device to re-establish its trust level. These flows are (a) a preparatory one where the device is enrolled in the ENTRUST domain and Blockchain network, the "Flow1: Preparing the Device for Trustworthiness Establishment", (b) the equipment of the device with the necessary crypto-primitives and the trust establishment for the first time storing all the necessary evidence in the Blockchain, namely the "Flow2: Establishing Device Trustworthiness", and (v) the re-establishment of trust upon identifying a new threat or risk that updates the stored information accordingly, the "Flow3: Re-establishing Device Trustworthiness". Figure 2 depicts these three main flows with different colours per sub-phase to be easily identifiable by the reader. More details are provided in the legend of the Figure 1.

4.1.1 Flow 1: Preparing the Device for Trustworthiness Establishment

This workflow focuses on the device preparations phase for trustworthiness establishment. Thus, the phase includes the device enrolment in ENTRUST Domain for supporting the zero-touch onboarding and registration to the Blockchain network. This workflow assumes that the Manufacturing (Design) Phase has already been performed and represents the Pre-deployment (Domain-specific) Phase, which includes all actions performed after the deployment of the device to the medical domain before its actual operation. Therefore, the RTL has already been calculated by the Manufacturer for the first time and the Device-level eMUD has already been created and stored in the MUD Server.

In the context of ENTRUST, there is the assumption that the Device-level eMUDs are managed by the MUD Server because this is considered an extension of the traditional/legacy MUD. However, for compliance purposes and to recommend a solution that is as less intrusive as possible when it comes to updates on legacy infrastructures, this type of Device-level eMUDs can be also securely managed by the Blockchain. The detailed steps of the flow are listed below starting from the enrolment of a device to a specific medical organization (domain), to its registration in the appropriate Blockchain channel, and finally to storing the device-level and the domain-level trust policies to the organization's Blockchain.

A - Domain Enrolment

“During this sub-phase a device wants to join a domain and thus a Domain-level eMUD for this device is created and stored on the public channel of the ENTRUST Blockchain for auditability purposes.”

(1) In this initial step, the device requests its eMUD (Device-level eMUD) URL from the MUD Server stored on the Manufacturer side. As already referred to in D3.2 [8], the Device-level eMUD extends the definition of the MUD profile standardized by the IETF in RFC 8520 including the **device’s Protection Profile** which contains the appropriate actions for the protection of the device based on the identified threats and vulnerabilities (e.g., list of threats defined by the manufacturer and the corresponding security enablers to mitigate them); a list of **Policy Hashes** for allowing the monitoring of the device’s operational evidence in a zero-knowledge manner, since these hashes represent the reference values of the device’s expected configuration and behaviour for safeguarding the use of the crypto primitives (Attestation Keys) established during the on-boarding; the pointer to the **Device-level Trust Policy**, a smart contract that dictates the evidence that needs to be collected in the ENTRUST Blockchain infrastructure and the type of Trusted Computing Base (TCB) used. Initially this field is empty since it is the first time that the device tries to join the domain and no specific evidence is needed to be collected.

(2) Then, the MUD Server provides the requested eMUD (e.g., Device-level eMUD) URL. This URL hosts all the necessary information for the device such as the identified threats, vulnerabilities, and associated security controls in an XML format.

(3) Upon the successful reception of the necessary information listed in the Device-level eMUD, the high-end device requests to enrol in the medical domain/organization forwarding the acquired Device-level eMUD URL to the Domain Manager. The domain enrolment implies that the device will not be in isolation as in the Manufacturing (Design) Phase and all the interdependences among the assets belonging to the Service Graph Chain (SGC) of the medical domain should be considered. This can be divided into two sub-phases: (i) The Authentication, Onboarding, and Enrolment of the device into the domain (see step 4), and (ii) the updating of the RTL of the device considering the medical domain infrastructure (see step 5), because this dictates the type of trustworthiness evidence that need to be monitored during runtime for the evaluation/calculation of the trust opinion of the device.

(4) The Domain Manager is responsible for the initiation of the actual authentication, onboarding, and enrolment to the domain. To do so, the Domain Manager triggers the Authentication Server of the Manufacturing domain, to ensure the authenticity of the device. Then, the Domain Manager based on the information extracted by the eMUD from the Blockchain, verifies that the enrolled devices are equipped with the correct key restriction usage policies enabling their later trust assessment and monitoring. More details regarding these workflows and cryptographic actions are provided in detail in the D4.2 [7].

(5a) In parallel, the Domain Manager along with the Domain Security Administrator's assistance initiates the risk assessment process and creates the risk graph considering the assets belonging to the specific medical domain and their interconnectivity. This leads to the update of the risk graph of the device with those additional attack vectors that become prominent once the device gets integrated into the target CMD domain. This, in turn, gets translated into a new RTL that will be part of the trust policy. The risk results include the risk quantification for the device and the security controls that could be enforced to mitigate them. In addition, the collective threat analysis of this process allows the Risk Assessment engine to contribute to the extension of the threat vectors to be included in the Domain-level eMUD per device. This process is done through the MUD Server, who is notified and ratifies the MUD profile.

(5b) The Risk Assessment engine shares the risk results across the ENTRUST architecture, including the Domain Security Administrator and the Domain Manager, which is depicted in Figure 2, continuously to ensure that they are up to date with the security posture of the device. More details regarding the Risk Assessment framework are provided in detail in the deliverable D3.2 [8].

(5c) The Risk Assessment engine works in tandem with the Trust Assessment Framework (TAF) for the trust assessment and initially generates the Device-level Trust Policy. When a device wants to join the domain generates the Domain-level Trust Policy. Both trust policies will be stored in the form of smart contracts in the private channel of the ledger. Note that the calculated RTL and the types of trust evidence (e.g., Remote Attestation, Configuration Integrity Verification, Control Flow Integrity, Swarm Attestation, Anomaly detection, etc.) to be collected to verify the correctness of the trust attributes are included in the trust policies. This evidence represents the necessary trust properties in the form of security claims, such as whether a device has the expected configuration integrity and/or has booted up correctly. Based on the type of evidence the Flow 2 Establishing Device Attestation will run accordingly. The trust policies essentially govern the entire trust assessment process. These Device-level and Domain-level trust policies are another innovation offered by ENTRUST towards the secure, efficient and auditable enforcement of security and trust policies.

(6) The Domain Manager extracts the key-restriction usage policies from the Device-level eMUD and verifies the successful enrolment of the device. These key restriction usage policies safeguard the use of the device’s attestation key. At this stage, the Domain Security Administrator elevates the enrolment request and generates the Domain-level eMUD per device, which includes the list of threats enriched with domain-specific vulnerabilities. The Domain-level eMUD per device will be stored in the public channel of the ENTRUST Blockchain network.

(7) The Domain Manager pushes the Domain-level eMUD on the ledger (as usual through the Security Context Broker (SCB) acting as mediator). Since the Domain-level eMUD will be stored on the public channel no access control check is needed.

(8) The SCB, as the bridge between the Blockchain network and the outside world, stores the Domain-level eMUD per device to the public channel of the Blockchain in the form of a smart contract (**SC1: Domain-level eMUD**).

B - Registration to BC channel

“During this sub-phase, the device registers to the ENTRUST Blockchain infrastructure in order to have access to the private channel. This sub-phase supports the two-layered access control mechanisms of ENTRUST.”

(1) At this stage we assume the device is already enrolled on the domain and wants to register to the specific private channel of the ENTRUST Blockchain infrastructure. To do so, the device requests to register to ENTRUST BC infrastructure at the target domain providing the domain ID acquired during the domain enrolment by the Domain Manager. As aforementioned, the domain ID is an attribute included in the issued VC and VP.

(2) The SCB forwards the request with the domain ID to the Membership Service Provider (MSP), an internal component of the Hyperledger Fabric Blockchain, to initiate the membership registration of the device.

(3) The MSP triggers the Blockchain CA, an internal component of the Hyperledger Fabric Blockchain, to issue the Blockchain identity certificate for the device that needs to be registered.

Such a Blockchain certificate This Blockchain certificate is for managing the access control capabilities of a components when interacting with the Blockchain. This is linked/binded to the Device's Verifiable Credential (VC) so as to make sure that no impersonation attacks can take place when interacting with the Blockchain.

(4) The issued certificate returned to the MSP for performing the access control at a later stage. These Blockchain certificates are not returned back to the device but are stored in the MSP.

C - Storing trust policies to BC channel

“During this sub-phase the Device-level Trust Policy and the Domain-level Trust Policy are generated or amended based on the trust opinion of TAF and stored on the private channel of ENTRUST Blockchain Infrastructure.”

(1) The TAF receives trustworthiness evidence from the devices based on which is calculates a device-level trust opinion and. Such opinions are then fused so as to convey the trust appraisal of the entire domain (see step A5c). As detailed n D3.2 [8], type of fusing operators to be deployed depends on the type of available trustworthiness evidence and the associated level of uncertainty/disbelief on the verifiability of such evidence.

(2) The trust policies along with the device's VP are forwarded to the SCB by the TAF for access control and then to invoke the corresponding smart contracts. As already mentioned, ENTRUST's authentication is a two-layered process.

(3a) The SCB interacts with the MSP to check the attributes of the Blockchain certificate issued by the Blockchain CA if the device has access to the specific Blockchain channel and then notifies the SCB whether the 1st authentication layer is successful or not.

(3b) If the 1st authentication layer is successful and the device has access to the requested channel, then the SCB performs an ABAC based on the provided VP from the high-end device, by invoking the corresponding smart contract of the channel.

(4a) The SCB invokes the corresponding smart contracts of the private channel to store the Device-level Trust Policy (**SC2: Device-level Trust Policy**) and the Domain-level Trust Policy (**SC3: Domain-level Trust Policy**).

(4b) The Blockchain pointers storing the Device-level Trust Policy and the domain-level Trust Policy are returned to the Domain Manager to amend the Device-level eMUD and the Domain-level eMUD respectively.

(4c) Then the Domain Manager notifies the MUD Server with the Device-level Trust Policy pointer and amends the stored Domain-level eMUD through the SCB with the Domain-level Trust Policy pointer (**SC1: Domain-level eMUD**).

4.1.2 Flow 2: Establishing Device Trustworthiness

This workflow focuses on the device's trustworthiness establishment. It includes storing the Conformity Certificates (CC), the application-related data, the attestation-related data, and the threat intelligence data in the Blockchain infrastructure. ENTRUST supports two modalities that trigger the trust assessment process a synchronous (e.g., TAF runs every two seconds) and an asynchronous one (e.g., if something is changed on a device). For instance, every time the RTL or the trust evidence/sources are updated initiate a new trust assessment process. We assume that a trust assessment process is initiated either synchronously or asynchronously and the TAF

component as the Verifier already collected the signatures of the trust evidence (see step E1b) to calculate the new trust opinion. Then TAF verifies the attestation evidence and appraises the actual level of trust ATL (quantify trust opinion).

D - Conformity Certificates

“During this sub-phase, TAF generates the Device-level CC or the Domain-level CC which are stored on the public channel of the ENTRUST ledger for auditability and certifiability purposes.”

Conformity Certificates (CC) support two modalities. A synchronous one, where an auditor requests it to verify the device or the domain's trustworthiness, and an asynchronous one, where the auditor defines a policy to generate CC periodically or when the trust state of the device or the domain changes.

(1a) Synchronous modality - A third-party auditor requests from TAF a CC to evaluate the trust level of the device (device-level CC) or the domain (domain-level CC).

(1b) Asynchronous modality - A third-party creates a policy to generate a Device-level CC or a Domain-level CC. Typical policies could generate the CC periodically or upon a change in a trust state.

(2a) The TAF generates a CC with the trust appraisal attributes, as defined in the Domain-level trust policy. This CC coming in the form of a VC (and protected under the p-ABC scheme) is then shared to the device from which it can selectively disclose only the information needed by the requesting auditor. And this VP is then stored on the Blockchain to be accessed by the auditor. And, of course, it can then be revoked by the SCB if there is a change in the trust level of the device.

(2b) TAF checks whether a valid CC (not an expired one) exists in the Blockchain to revoke it. Revocation will not affect the auditability of the information stored. So, this authenticated revocation will be safeguarded through the appropriate crypto schemes as an extension to the p-ABC protocol. Note that the exact revocation protocol will be defined in the context of D4.3.

(3) The issued CC is then sent to the device (3a) if it is a Device-level CC or the Domain Manager (3b) if it is a Domain-level CC.

(4) The device (4a) or the Domain Manager (4b) generates a Privacy Attribute-Based Credentials (p-ABC) VC that selectively discloses through zero-knowledge proofs only the attributes requested by the auditor, as described in D3.2 [8]. Also, note that the high-end devices can utilize such p-ABC mechanism for selective disclosure, while the low-end devices that do not have the necessary crypto ability present the issued from TAF VC as is, which is bound to the outcomes of the PUF.

(5) The SCB invokes the corresponding smart contracts of the public channel to store the Device-level CC (**SC4: Device-level CC**) (5a) and the Domain-level CC (**SC5: Domain-level CC**) (5b).

E - Attestation

“During this sub-phase, TAF requests attestation trust evidence, as has been defined in the corresponding Trust Policy of the device.”

ENTRUST is based on the provision of various trustworthiness evidence based on which the trust assessment can be conducted. Such trust sources can stem from attestation enablers, the AI-

based anomaly detection enablers, etc. The combination of such evidence can allow the trust opinion calculation for different properties of trust including integrity, safety, resilience, etc. All trust models have been described in the context of D3.2 [8]. In the context of ENTRUST, the high-end devices are equipped with a Trusted Execution Environment (TEE), while the low-end devices with a PUF-based Trusted Computing Base (TCB), both comprise a Trusted Computing Base anchored to a different secure element depending on the capabilities/resources of the underlying host. The following steps are performed in the case where the needed trust evidence (see step A5c) is attestation.

(1) The medical device generates attestation-related data, upon a request from the TAF based on the trust sources been identified inside the trust policy. More specifically, all devices generate attestation evidence in the form of signature, where the high-end devices can also generate attestation reports for the low-end devices since they do not have the capability of directly communicating with the TAF. Attestation evidence is stored off-chain, after been encrypted with ABE, and the pointers are stored on-chain (1a), while the attestation signatures are collected by the TAF for the trust assessment (1b).

(2a) The SCB interacts with the MSP to check the attributes of the Blockchain certificate issued by the Blockchain CA if the device has access to the specific Blockchain channel and then notifies the SCB whether the 1st authentication layer is successful or not.

(2b) If the 1st authentication layer is successful and the device has access to the requested channel.

(3) The SCB invokes the specific smart contract and based on the provided VP from the high-end device allows or not to access the private channel for storing the attestation raw data and the attestation report (**SC6: Attestation**).

(4) If the data exceeds the volume limitation on the ENTRUST ledger, then the data are forwarded to the ABE component enabling fine-grained access control over encrypted data. In general, this applies to the attestation raw data.

(5) After the successful encryption the encrypted data is stored off the chain.

(6) The corresponding storage pointer is forwarded back to the private ledger invoking the same smart contract to amend it with this information.

F - Application and network data

“During this sub-phase the AI-based anomaly detection component identifies potential threats/vulnerabilities based on the retrieved application data and network traces of the device. The newly identified threat intelligence is harmonized and formatted in STIX format for privacy-preservation and interoperability. Such information is stored on the public Hygiene Marketplace channel of the ENTRUST Blockchain.”

The following steps are performed in the case where the required trust evidence (see step A5c) is the output of the AI-based anomaly detection component of the Digital Twins.

(1a) The medical device generates application data and network tracing for monitoring the system behaviour within the context of a specific application (e.g., the time that the application binary runs, the CPU lifecycle, and host and networking data specific to the target application). Then the application-related data and network traces along with the VP are pushed to the ledger through the SCB.

(1b) In parallel, application-related data and network traces are forwarded to Digital Twins which runs internally the AI-based anomaly detection to further research for new threats and vulnerabilities.

(1c) Digital Twins and its internal anomaly detection functionality analyse the data for potential new threats. If a new threat is identified by anomaly detection, a new risk assessment process is triggered for calculating the updated RTL.

(1d) If the ATL is less than the newly calculated RTL, the risk assessment initiates mitigation actions such as the SW update process (**#SC9 Policy Enforcement**). This scenario results in an updated Device-level eMUD triggered by the SW Service Provider. The Domain Manager is then notified and initiates the process of updating the device policy hashes (e.g., the key restriction usage policies) in a verifiable manner.

(2) If no threats are identified, Digital Twins generates the harmonized and privacy-preserving threat intelligence data in STIX format. These newly generated data are forwarded to the Hygiene Marketplace channel through the SCB (2a). The same data are also forwarded to the TAF (and the Risk Assessment) as an additional trust source (2b).

(3) The SCB invokes the specific smart contract of the private channel for the application data and network source (**SC7: Application data and network traces**).

(4) If the data exceeds the volume limitation on the ledger, then is forwarded to the ABE to be encrypted.

(5) After the successful encryption the encrypted data is stored off the chain.

(6) The corresponding storage pointer is forwarded back to the private ledger invoking the same smart contract to amend it with this information.

(7) The SCB invokes the specific smart contract of the Hygiene Marketplace channel for the harmonized threat intelligence data (**SC8: Harmonised Threat Intelligence data**). It is crucial to note here the threat intelligence data are in STIX format, that abstracts any sensitive information from the data to be shared with other domains.

4.1.3 Flow 3: Re-establishing Device Trustworthiness

This workflow focuses on the device’s trustworthiness re-establishment (e.g., when there is a failed attestation or when the ATL is lower than the RTL) leading to the definition of a security policy that is enforced, dictating for instance a SW/FW Update, for which updated reference values on the device’s expected configuration and behaviour need to be enforced. This is another innovation of ENTRUST that allows this operation to be performed in a secure manner without the need for the device to re-register to the domain.

G - Failed Attestation or Change in the trust-level of the device

“During this sub-phase a failed attestation or a change on the trust-level of the device initiates the re-establishment of trust by enforcing a mitigation action such as a SW/FW update.”

(1) In the case of a failed attestation or in the case of a trust level change, due to some monitor trustworthiness evidence (e.g. attestation reports or identified misbehaviours), TAF notifies the Digital Twins to get the raw evidence for further processing (e.g., application data and network

traces). This further processing includes the attack emulation to identify the concrete attack execution path (and is done by the internal sub-component Attack Emulation).

(2) The output of the Attack Emulation part of the Digital Twins is forwarded to the SW/FW Verification service instantiated in the backend as described in D3.2 [8], for the fuzzing test cases. Based on these test cases the Security Administrator will be able to create the updated SW binary with the necessary patches.

(3) This new SW update is forwarded to the Secure SW Update service instantiated in the backend, which along with the Digital Twins and its Subfleet Manager subcomponent help is pushed to the recipient devices.

(4) The receiving device through its internal attestation enablers will provide the necessary evidence to the TAF for checking whether now is ATL has increased above the RTL due to the updated software.

4.2 Architectural Building Blocks

This section describes the internal building blocks of the ENTRUST conceptual Blockchain architecture followed by supplementary functionalities and components, including among others the Attribute-based Access Control (ABAC) and Membership Service Provider (MSP), Security Context Broker (SCB), Off-chain data storage and Attribute-based Encryption (ABE), MUD Server, Domain Manager, Risk Assessment (RA), Trust Assessment Framework (TAF) and Digital Twins, etc., and we elaborate on how those components exploit the Blockchain architecture to enable their operations.

4.2.1 Hyperledger Fabric - ENTRUST Private/Public Ledger and Channels

Blockchain Node: A Blockchain Node is a crucial element within the ENTRUST blockchain network, tasked with hosting the chaincode that executes smart contract functions and managing the ledgers where transaction details are recorded. The blockchain node interacts with entities of the ENTRUST framework such as the CMDs, the Domain Manager, and the MUD Server, through the Security Context Broker (SCB) to ensure the secure recording and retrieval of information like trust policies and attestation evidence within the ENTRUST blockchain infrastructure. The Blockchain node is an abstraction decentralized layer for allowing interacting with the Blockchain, while the inclusion of SCB is a centralized design choice for allowing ENTRUST to have better control and agility on safeguarding who transact with the on and off chain data. This interaction enables the execution of smart contracts. Operating independently, each blockchain node maintains its copy of the Private (per domain) and Public Ledger and plays a key role in the ENTRUST blockchain by conducting operations, maintaining ledgers, and participating in consensus processes. These consensus processes are essential for executing transactions and securely integrating them into the blockchain network. Within the ENTRUST framework, the approach is not to assign a single blockchain node per CMD but to organize an appropriate number of blockchain nodes to ensure the optimal management of blockchain operations. The ideal number of Blockchain Peers to support the various CMDs of the ENTRUST framework will be detailed in deliverables D6.1 and D6.2 as part of the evaluation activities under WP6.

Private Ledger: Within the ENTRUST framework, a Private Ledger is deployed per domain. Private Ledger is responsible for the storage of (a) the hashes for the auditability of the smart contracts that have been executed concerning the recording and retrieval of information such as attestation evidence and trust policies, (b) the data blobs capturing all these data management transactions (e.g., off-chain storage pointers) as well as (c) the security and trust policy enforcement. ENTRUST users and devices that comprise the ENTRUST ecosystem once

registered are automatically notified of any new data item been pushed on the chain (e.g., trustworthiness evidence, new trust appraisal) that can then query if they are authorised to access the specific data blob.

Public Ledger: A Public Ledger is deployed for the entire ENTRUST framework. The Public Ledger enables the storage of Conformity Certificates (CC) for the operation of the CMDs in ENTRUST and facilitates the revocation of these conformity certificates in case the attestation of the corresponding CMDs fails. CCs are stored publicly to be available to any certification and auditing entity that would like to check the trustworthiness level of operation of CMDs in ENTRUST. The Domain-level eMUDs, which contain the collective list of threats for the medical devices of the domain, are also stored in the Public Ledger. In addition, another public channel is the Hygiene Marketplace for storing the threat intelligence information with other verticals of the medical domain.

Channels: Channels are a core concept in the context of Hyperledger Fabric for achieving privacy, confidentiality, and scalability within Blockchain networks. Channels ensure that transactions are only visible to authorized parties. Also, it helps in optimizing network performance by segregating transactions into different channels. Segregation enables Hyperledger Fabric to process a higher volume of transactions simultaneously without affecting network performance. Additionally, it provides flexibility in network configurations, as channels can be dynamically created and managed to meet diverse business needs and use cases. In addition, channels also play a significant role in facilitating interoperability among different organizations within the Hyperledger Fabric ecosystem. Such a feature can foster seamless collaboration and communication among different healthcare organizations. It must also be noted that ENTRUST goes a step further supporting not only access control on the channel level, but also to the data level, achieving much more agility and granularity. In the context of channel-level access control, ENTRUST leverage Fabric’s membership services (check the 1st level of authorization in the ENTRUST Blockchain) to manage identities and permissions, ensuring that only authorized CMDs and entities can join and interact with the channel. The ENTRUST architecture supports three different channels, as already stated in the introduction part of this chapter; the public channel, the private channel, and the Hygiene Marketplace channel, another public channel, for storing different data of the ENTRUST with different privacy requirements and needs.

Blockchain Certificate Authority (CA): The Blockchain Certificate Authority (Blockchain CA) is a critical component that handles the issuance and management of digital certificates for CMDs that desire to access the ENTRUST blockchain infrastructure. These certificates are used for identity verification, ensuring that only authorized CMDs can enter the ENTRUST Ledgers. The Blockchain CA allows new CMDs to register in the ENTRUST DLT network and enables registered CMDs to request a digital certificate through the SCB and the MSP for accessing the ENTRUST DLT. The public keys that are embedded in the certificates are based on the Elliptic Curve Digital Signature Algorithm (ECDSA). In ENTRUST we are merging such legacy identity management solutions with the adoption of self-sovereign identity (SSI) management capabilities, thus enabling users and devices to disclose only those identity attributes needed for accessing a data item.

APIs and Interfaces: The API layer serves as a bridge for communication and interaction between external entities (such as the Domain Manager and the MUD Server) and the DLT. This layer provides the interfaces that external entities invoke, managing the communication between Blockchain Nodes and the Security Context Broker. By leveraging the API layer, integration with smart contracts is achieved, facilitating transactions and the recording or retrieval of data. Additionally, the API layer plays a crucial role in finalizing transactions before they are sent for

ordering in the Blockchain, organizing essential details before submission for storage in the ENTRUST blockchain infrastructure.

4.2.2 Membership Service Provider (MSP) and Attribute-based Access Control (ABAC)

ENTRUST supports a two-layer access control mechanism based on Hyperledger Fabric's MSP mechanism and the well-known ABAC. Initially, the SCB communicates with the MSP to enroll and get the appropriate credentials (e.g., certificates) from the blockchain CA based on which access to a specific channel is granted (1st authentication layer). Then, the ABAC that works closely with the SCB interacts with the Peer Nodes to maintain effective access control on the blockchain through the usage of smart contracts and Verifiable Presentations (VPs) provided by the high-end devices (2nd authentication layer). VCs are stored on the Verifiable Credentials Management component, part of the high-end devices TCB (e.g., enclave). Then the high-end devices generate the necessary Verifiable Presentation (VP) to request access to the ENTRUST blockchain infrastructure. The low-end devices access the blockchain through the high-end device, by providing credentials issued during enrollment. An authentication mechanism exists between the low-end and high-end devices as already explained in D4.2 [7].

The Membership Service Provider (MSP) serves as a bridge between the CMDs and the Security Context Broker for the CMDs to obtain access to the ENTRUST Blockchain infrastructure. Eventually, each time the CMD desires to get access to the ENTRUST Blockchain by sending a corresponding request to the SCB, the SCB sends a message to the MSP to request the certificate to check whether the CMD is indeed registered to the ENTRUST Blockchain, fulfilling in this way the 1st level of authorization in the ENTRUST Blockchain.

Attribute-Based Access Control (ABAC) is an advanced access control mechanism that utilizes attributes as the basis for managing access to resources. Unlike traditional methods that rely solely on roles or predefined rules, ABAC evaluates access requests based on various attributes linked to users, resources, and environmental conditions. These attributes can include user roles, departments, locations, times of access, and the sensitivity of the resources. The core ABAC components are:

- **Policy Decision Point (PDP)** - Evaluates access requests against established policies, considering attributes of the requester, resource, and environment to make informed access decisions.
- **Policy Enforcement Point (PEP)** - Enforces the access decisions made by the PDP, ensuring only authorized users access the requested resources.
- **Policy Information Point (PIP)**: Retrieves additional attribute information required by the PDP.
- **Policy Administration Point (PAP)** - Manages and defines the policies, enabling administrators to create, update, and delete policies according to organizational needs.

ABAC offers several advantages, including fine-grained access control, adaptability to changing conditions, scalability for complex structures, and flexibility in policy management. This flexible, precise, and dynamic approach enhances both security and operational efficiency. These characteristics led the ENTRUST consortium to adopt ABAC for access control to the information stored on the Blockchain as an additional authentication mechanism (2nd level of authorization), working in tandem with the Security Context Broker (SCB).

Figure 3 ABAC sequence diagram

More specifically, when an already onboarded device desires to get access to the Blockchain and has successfully passed through the 1st level of authorization by having a valid Blockchain certificate, it shall also communicate with the SCB to have its issued Verifiable Presentations checked by the ABAC. The ABAC is closely interrelated with the SCB and is responsible for leveraging the necessary access control mechanisms based on specific attributes to decide whether a device shall be granted access to the channels of the ENTRUST DLT. If the Verifiable Presentations (domain ID and other trustworthiness attributes) of the device are satisfying the designated access policies of the ABAC, the SCB sends a message to the device for obtaining access to the ENTRUST Blockchain.

4.2.3 Security Context Broker (SCB)

The Security Context Broker (SCB) serves as the exclusive intermediary between the ENTRUST Blockchain infrastructure and external entities (e.g., ENTRUST components), that can transform the data during storage and retrieval in the ledger. Therefore, SCB gives the flexibility to perform actions that would be really consuming in the Blockchain, while SCB does not have limitations on the data format that it receives from the devices. SCB is responsible to transform data transactions received from Blockchain Nodes into smart contract logic, which is then deployed on the ENTRUST Blockchain. It facilitates communication and interaction between the various components of the ENTRUST system and Blockchain smart contracts through APIs, serving as a trusted mediator. Its main function is to initiate the execution of smart contract operations, ensuring efficient message transmission and connecting different components to the Blockchain. Additionally, the SCB enforces ABAC mechanisms to ensure that only components with the required attributes (check of VPs as a 2nd level of authorization in the ENTRUST Blockchain) can access or query specific data on the Blockchain in close collaboration with the Membership

Service Provider (MSP). Besides interacting with Blockchain Nodes, the SCB is also interconnected with the Off-Chain Data Storage to manage the storage and retrieval of data of sensitive or large-size nature that are not directly stored in the Private Ledger.

4.2.4 Off-chain data storage and Attribute-based Encryption (ABE)

The Off-Chain Data Storage is designed to hold encrypted data that due to their sensitivity or large-size nature cannot be stored directly on the ENTRUST Blockchain. However, the encrypted pointers to these data are maintained in the Private Ledger, indicating the location of the stored information in the Off-Chain Data Storage. These pointers utilize ABE techniques to ensure data security within ENTRUST, allowing access only to authorized entities. ENTRUST entities gain access to the off-chain storage through interaction with the Security Context Broker and the application of ABAC policies, ensuring controlled and secure data handling.

4.2.5 Other Blockchain-dependent ENTRUST Entities and Artifacts

For completeness purposes, we describe in this subsection the blockchain-dependent entities and artifacts of ENTRUST.

MUD Server: The MUD Server, located on the Manufacturer's side, and as its name suggests, host the eMUD files.

Domain Manager: The Domain Manager, as its name suggests, is responsible for authentication, onboarding, and enrolment to the domain (e.g., healthcare organization). In a nutshell, is a centralized server on the Domain's side that acts as an orchestrator of the domain from the bootstrapping of the domain up to the runtime operation, trust assessment and possibly reconfiguration of the domain in case of a risk indicator. Interacts with several components of the ENTRUST architecture such as the high-end devices that want to be authenticated, the Authentication Server to ensure the authenticity of the device, the TAF and Risk Assessment for managing trust assessment and risk evaluation processes, and the SCB for storing or retrieving information to/from the blockchain. During onboarding, the Domain Manager is responsible for the correct bootstrap of the device prior to be enrolled.

Risk Assessment (RA) Engine and Mitigation Policy Enforcement: The Risk Assessment is a core component on the Domain's side that shares the risk results across the ENTRUST architecture in a continuous manner. The component performs a thorough threat analysis including the identification of underlying threats and vulnerabilities of a CMD isolated and within the domain context to evaluate the risk and identify potential security controls that can be enforced. Also, this component works in tandem with the TAF for the calculation of RTL based on which the trustworthiness of the topology can be evaluated during runtime. Last, but not least, the RA can enforce mitigation actions to minimize the calculated risks. More details regarding its internal architecture and quantification process are provided in the D3.2 [8].

Trust Assessment Framework: The Trust Assessment Framework (TAF) is a core component on the Domain's side that is responsible for handling the trust assessment process of ENTRUST to verify whether a device is in a trustworthy state or not. TAF calculates of the ATL of the CMD, which reflects the actual level of trust of the device during runtime based on the attestation output. The ATL is then compared with the previously calculated RTL indicating the baseline level of trust that needs to be achieved to determine whether the device can be considered trustworthy or not. More details regarding TAF's internal architecture and functionalities are provided in the D3.2 [8].

Digital Twins, AI-based anomaly detection, and Secure SW/FW update: The digital representation of the medical devices is the Digital Twins, located in the domain side, which monitors the CMD's behavior and any necessary information such as bandwidth or energy

consumption. In a nutshell, this component mirrors its real-time dynamics within a controlled environment enabling the emulation of potential attacks targeting the CMD in a secure and isolated environment, leading to the identification of new threats and zero-day vulnerabilities. Part of this component is also the AI-based Intrusion Detection process that could identify any deviation from the expected behavior of the CMD. Any identified threat or zero-day vulnerability (e.g., threat intelligence data) is stored on the Hygiene Marketplace Channel of the blockchain infrastructure. This threat intelligence data is also forwarded to the RA to re-calculate the updated RTL. In addition, this component provides the basis for the Secure SW/FW Update mechanisms of ENTRUST whereupon an identified threat or vulnerability that could change the trustworthiness level of the CMD, the Digital Twins can deploy a SW/FW update securely to address and mitigate the issue.

Verifiable Credentials Management (Enclave): This component is an internal part of the devices ENTRUST TCB. As its name suggests, is responsible for managing and constructing the VPs for both disclosing in a zero-knowledge manner any system properties that depict the device's trust level, but also for selecting disclosing identity attributes for the device's authentication purposes.

Privacy Certificate Authority: The Privacy Certificate Authority (Privacy CA) is a pivotal entity that manages the issuance and validation of digital certificates, ensuring secure communications within the ENTRUST framework. The Privacy CA oversees the creation of cryptographic identities for CMDs, which are essential for authentication and authorization in ENTRUST DLT. The Privacy CA is a trusted third party that issues the Verifiable Credentials (VCs) of a CMD, containing its attributes, during the secure enrolment phase of the CMD. A subset of these VCs, named Verifiable Presentations (VPs), are used for the authorization of the CMD towards accessing the ENTRUST DLT in a privacy-aware manner.

5 Smart Contracts in ENTRUST

In ENTRUST, the implementation of smart contract functions is driven by the objective of facilitating secure, transparent, and automated operations within the ENTRUST Blockchain framework. ENTRUST smart contracts introduce innovative approaches for managing trustworthiness evidence data like attestation evidence, application data and network traces, threat intelligence information, and conformity certificates, and ensuring data integrity and confidentiality across the network.

Smart contract languages, such as Solidity and Go, feature the traits of object-oriented programming (OOP) languages, including inheritance which is a mechanism that allows a class (e.g., child) to inherit properties and behaviors from another class (e.g., parent). Inheritance is a fundamental concept in OOP that promotes code reuse, organization and establishes relationships between classes. Thus, inheritance allows a child contract to access functionalities from other contracts called base or parent contracts and to override a function in that base contract. This capability of hierarchical management and access of data fields between smart contracts, are specifically focused on the distinction between device-level and domain-level trust management. Such a feature allows the efficient elevation of device-level data management to domain-level data management. For instance, imagine that a domain comprising multiple devices each one of which is govern by a different trust policy and each one of this trust policies including a different RTL per device they need to be fused so as to facilitate the construction of the domain-level trust policies, meaning that the RTL needs to be fused in a suitable way to calculate the domain-level RTL. The inheritance feature can support the efficient access to these data with the minimal number of required transactions. More details regarding the implementation aspect of ENTRUST smart contracts will be provided in the D6.1. However, below we summarize the four types of inheritance¹⁸:

- **Single Inheritance** - In this type, as its name suggests, functions and variables of one base contract are inherited to only one derived contract.
- **Multi-level Inheritance** - In this type, the difference is that it has levels of the relationship between the parent and the child. The child contract derived from a parent also acts as a parent for the contract which is derived from it.
- **Hierarchical Inheritance** - In this type, a parent contract has more than one child contracts.
- **Multiple Inheritance** - In this type, a single contract can be inherited from many contracts. Thus, a parent contract can have more than one child while a child contract can have more than one parent.

5.1 Types of Smart Contracts

Considering the primary reasons for utilizing Blockchain technology paved the way for identifying the different smart contract types. These reasons are the auditability and integrity of the data flows needed to support ENTRUST's trust assessment process and the enforcement of trust policies in

¹⁸ <https://www.geeksforgeeks.org/solidity-inheritance/>

an auditable and verifiable manner. To capture these reasons several types of smart contracts are deployed in ENTRUST Blockchain architecture. These are summarised in the following table.

Table 2: Smart Contract Types

Smart Contract Types	Description
Extended MUD smart contracts (#SC1 - Domain-level eMUD per device)	Extended MUD contracts manage eMUD files for all devices comprising a domain (e.g. Domain-level eMUD). This keeps all the threats for the specific device and the expected version of SW/FW, in the same way as the Device-level eMUD and also the extended set of threats considering possible attack vectors within the domain stemming from the relationships to be created by the target device with the other domain stakeholders.
Trust policies smart contracts (#SC2 - Device-level Trust Policy and #SC3 - Domain-level Trust Policy)	Trust policies as contracts manage the trust model based on which both device-level and domain-level trust assessment is done. Trust models keep representations of the “relationship graph” that the target device needs to establish with the other devices comprising the domain and for those trust properties of interest. Thus, a trust relationship between the trustor Device A and trustee Device B for integrity is for instance part of this trust model. Trust property of interest depicts the trust assessment to be done for this specific node (device-level trust) whereas the trust opinion calculation on a relationship represents the domain-level trust. Trust policies keep all the necessary information governing the trust assessment process such as the RTL, the list of trust evidence/sources as well as the history of the ATL values for each device and subsequently each domain.
Conformity Certificate smart contracts (#SC4 Device-level CC #SC5 Domain-level CC)	Conformity Certificate contracts manage the Device-level CC and the Domain-level CC. In the context of low-end devices, the generation of the CC is done during the onboarding phase since we are primarily focusing on auditing of static properties like the output of the secure boot. Thus, the CCs are created by the TAF and are binded to a multitude set of one-time signatures so that the low-end device can present them upon request in an authenticated manner with freshness guarantees. This binding is achieved by the use of Merkle-trees as described in D4.2 [7].
Attestation-related smart contracts (#SC6 Attestation)	Attestation-related contracts are crucial for managing the attestation process within ENTRUST. These contracts handle the creation, storage and sharing of attestation reports from the high-end devices representing their trust state or forwarded by the high-end devices represented the trust state of the low-end devices leveraging the mechanism described in D4.2 [7]. In addition, these contracts verify the authenticity and integrity of the encrypted raw attestation data stored off the chain.
Application-related smart contracts (#SC7 Application data and network traces)	Application-related contracts are designed to manage and govern the application-related data and network traces within the ENTRUST

	platform. These contracts handle the creation, storage and sharing of application-related data as described in D4.2 [7].
Threat intelligence-related smart contracts <i>#SC8 Threat intelligence data</i>	These contracts are designed to manage and govern the threat intelligence data in a harmonized and privacy-preserving STIX format. These contracts ensure the audibility and integrity of data as it is shared across the ENTRUST network.
Policy enforcement smart contracts <i>(#SC9 Policy Enforcement)</i>	Policy enforcement contracts automate the enforcement of mitigation strategies such as SW/FW update or leveraging an IDS.
Trust template smart contracts <i>(#SC10 Trust Template)</i>	Trust template contracts are designed to manage a trust model. More specifically, it defines the relationships of a trust model based on some events.

At this point, we need to highlight that ENTRUST secures the lifecycle of these transactions by providing also innovative schemes of ABAC as part of the audit chain execution of a contract. Thus, a user to access to a data blob must selectively disclose a required set of attributes. These attributes are selectively disclosed through the Attribute-based Signcryption scheme encoded in VPs, as described in D4.2 [7]. Essentially, these presentations are comprised of attribute-based signatures and attribute-based encrypted challenges (e.g., Attribute-based Signcryption) based on policies represented through access control trees. For instance, only a certified auditor can have access to a specific set of data or only the OEM/manufacture can have access to any raw traces that represent a failed attestation all the way to system properties and device characteristics.

5.2 Smart Contract Functions for Data Management

This section outlines the different types of smart contracts driven by the objective of facilitating secure and transparent operations within the ENTRUST Blockchain framework. To this end, the tables below detail the smart contract functions that have been developed or are planned for the second release of the ENTRUST Blockchain platform. Note that there are two types of smart contract functions:

- **Exported (E):** Functions responsible for calling and implementing smart contracts of the ENTRUST Blockchain infrastructure, typically starting with an uppercase letter.
- **Unexported (U):** Sub-functions and variables that necessitate a smart contract to operate as designed, usually starting with a lowercase letter.

Table 2: Data sharing workflows

Type	Smart Contract Function	Description	Release	Accountable
E	AuthenticateUserBCCert ()	Authenticates a user's Blockchain certificate before allowing access to sensitive functions and Blockchain channels. This functionality utilizes the MSP-based Fabric's authentication and	1.0	SCB

		is the 1st check of ENTRUST's two-layered access control mechanism.		
E	PostApplicationData()	This function is responsible for creating a smart contract to govern the process of initiating and collecting the necessary application data (e.g., data produced by the AI-based misbehavior, network data and traces) and finally storing them. To do so, it invokes the function storeApplicationData() to create the pointers and store the data in the Off-Chain Data Storage.	1.0	SCB
E	PostTrustworthinessEvidence()	This function is responsible for creating a smart contract to govern the process of initiating and collecting the necessary trustworthiness evidence (e.g., attestation evidence or AI-based misbehavior detection output) in accordance with the Trust Policy that applies and finally storing them. The Domain Manager checks the Trust Policy and triggers the high-end device accordingly to initiate the trustworthiness evidence collection. Upon receiving the evidence the SCB executes the storeAttestationData() function to create the pointers and store the data in the Off-Chain Data Storage. Then, TAF is automatically notified when new trust evidence exists to get the on-chain pointers and the evidence from the Off-Chain Data Storage.	1.0	SCB
U	storeApplicationData()	This function is invoked by SCB upon reception of a request, invokes the getAccess() to check whether the requestor entity has the required set of attributes, and if the requestor is authorized invokes the storeOffChainDataAndDBPointer() to store the application-related data in the Fabric ledger. When needed Off-Chain Data Storage is also utilized.	1.0	Fabric Ledger + Off-Chain Data Storage
U	storeAttestationData()	This function is invoked by SCB upon reception of a request, invokes the getAccess() to check whether the requestor entity has the required set of attributes, and if the requestor is authorized invokes the storeOffChainDataAndDBPointer() to store the attestation report in the Fabric ledger. When needed Off-Chain Data Storage is also utilized.	1.0	Fabric Ledger + Off-Chain Data Storage
U	getAccess()	This function is called when an action needs to have a certain set of properties and is invoked as part of	2.0	SCB, ABAC, ABE

		every transaction since it offers the orthogonal functionality of access control. It is related to the 2nd authentication check of ENTRUST's two-layer access control which is based on the ABAC and VPs. ENTRUST's VPs are constructed according to the Signcryption scheme documented in D4.2 [7]. On top of that, this function is also related to the ABE mechanisms where data can only be read by a device with certain characteristics.		
U	storeOffChainDataAndDBPointer()	This function is responsible for securely storing data in the offline database, the Off-Chain Data Storage. The pointer that is produced with this function is saved on the ledger, and it links to the data that was sent. For example, raw traces, produced as part of the attestation evidence report, are first encrypted with the ABE, and then stored in the Off-Chain Data Storage. The pointer created with this function points to these encrypted traces, is appended to the previous trustworthiness evidence report, and is also stored on the ledger.	2.0	Fabric Ledger + Off-Chain Data Storage + ABE
E	QueryApplicationData()	This function is responsible for retrieving the stored application-related data. First, it invokes the getAccess() function to check the authorization of the requestor and then queries the application data (e.g., network traces and AI-based misbehavior output) maintained in the ledger. This function is usually invoked by AI-based misbehavior detection or external auditoros.	1.0	Fabric Ledger + Off-Chain Data Storage + SCB
E	QueryAttestationData()	This function is responsible for retrieving the stored attestation-related data. First, it invokes the getAccess() function to check the authorization of the requestor and then queries the attestation reports maintained in the ledger. This function is usually invoked by TAF or external auditoros.	1.0	Fabric Ledger + Off-Chain Data Storage + SCB
E	PostTrustPolicy()	This function is responsible for creating a smart contract to govern the process of trust policy creation. To do so it invokes first the getAccess() and then the createTrustPolicy() function.	2.0	SCB
U	createTrustTemplate ()	This function is responsible for creating the trust template. Based on this, the trust model is created/amended and is	2.0	Fabric Ledger + SCB

		what initiates the process of creating a trust policy.		
U	createTrustPolicy()	This function is responsible for creating the necessary characteristics for governing the trust assessment process. It defines the parameters that are needed including the RTL either per device or per domain, the type of trustworthiness evidence to be collected, the record/history of the ATL, and periodicity (for synchronous communication).	2.0	Fabric Ledger + SCB
E	QueryTrustLevel()	This function exposes an interface to give access to the trust level of the device or domain to authorized external entities/components/users. The actual trust level per device or an abstraction of it is returned (trust appraisal for the domain).	2.0	Fabric Ledger + SCB
U	applySecurityPolicy()	This function manages the enforcement of security policies related to any mitigation strategies as a result to an attack.	2.0	SCB + Risk Assessment + Mitigation Policy Enforcement
E	PostThreatIntelligenceData()	This function is responsible for creating a smart contract to govern the process of collecting the harmonized threat intelligence data in STIX representation by the Risk Assessment based on the output provided by the Attack Emulation Component (part of the Digital Twins) and storing them in the Hygiene Marketplace channel of the ENTRUST ledger. It also invokes the getAccess() function to check the authorization.	2.0	Fabric Ledger + SCB
E	QueryThreatIntelligenceData()	This function is responsible for retrieving the stored harmonized threat intelligence data. First, it invokes the getAccess() function to check the authorization of the requestor and then queries the threat intelligence data maintained in the Hygiene Marketplace channel of the ledger.	2.0	Fabric Ledger + SCB
U	storeeMUD()	The manufacturer's MUD server interacts with the Domain Manager and along with the assistance of the Domain Security Administrator generates the Domain-level eMUD per device. This function is responsible for storing the eMUD profile (e.g., the Domain-level eMUD per device) on the Blockchain ledger.	2.0	Fabric Ledger
U	updateeMUD()	This function is responsible for deploying a smart contract that allows	2.0	Fabric Ledger

		an authorized stakeholder or external component to access and modify the latest update and key restriction policy hash properties of the Domain-level eMUD of a device.		
E	QueryeMUD()	This function queries with specific attributes (e.g., DeviceID, Version, Policy, etc.) from the Domain-level eMUD per device that is stored in the Blockchain ledger.	2.0	Fabric Ledger
U	storeCC()	This function is responsible for storing the Device or Domain-level CC on the Blockchain ledger. Low-end devices' CC is also accompanied by a challenge which is also stored on the ledger for verification purposes.	2.0	Fabric Ledger
E	QueryCC()	This function is called to retrieve the stored CC either per device or per domain.	2.0	Fabric Ledger

5.3 Smart Contract Data Model Definition

This section delves into details on the type of data that each type of smart contract manages in accordance with the previous defined functions. Chaincode is the Hyperledger Fabric's version of smart contracts that runs on a Blockchain network and encapsulates the business logic. Every smart contract has also an endorsement policy attached to it. It must be noted here that the grey colour highlights the inherited fields in the data model Tables below. Also, the data model represents the state variables of the smart contract. More specifically, ENTRUST supports a Device-level CC and a Domain-level CC per medical device. Thus, in this case Single Inheritance is supported, where the Domain-level CC (child) inherits from the Device-level CC (parent):

**Domain-level CC is
 Device-level CC**

In addition, ENTRUST supports one trust policy per device which is then elevated as part of the one trust policy per domain. But we can have multiple trust models per policy. the multiple inheritance feature. Thus, in this case Multiple Inheritance is supported, where the Domain-level Trust Policy (child) inherits the Device-level Trust Policy from all the medical devices (parents) enrolled in the specific domain:

**Domain1-level Trust Policy is
 Device1-level CC Trust Policy &
 Device2-level CC Trust Policy &
 Device3-level CC Trust Policy**

**Domain2-level Trust Policy is
 Device1-level CC Trust Policy &
 Device2-level CC Trust Policy**

Table 21 Application-data Data Structure

Name	Data Type	JSON Schema	Description
reportID	string	json:" reportID "	A string identifier used as a unique key to identify application-specific data.
deviceID	string	json:" deviceID "	A string identification used to identify the device derived from application related data.
createdAt	string	json:"createdAt"	The application report comprises a string identification that represents the date of its creation (e.g., timestamp).
listOfAttributes	[] string	json:" listofattributes"	This field refers to the list of attributes that a device or party must possess, to be able to read this particular application report.
Result	[] string	json:" result"	Includes the indications of each device depending on what kind of device is mentioned each time, for example a device measure temperature the result could be "temperature: 68°F "
Signature	string	json:" signature"	Signature of the medical device.
DBpointer	string	json:" DBPointer"	Pointer to off-chain

Table 22 Attestation-report Data Structure

Name	Data Type	JSON Schema	Description
reportID	string	json:" reportID "	A string identifier that serves as a unique key for representing a given attestation report.
deviceID	string	json:" deviceID "	A string identifier pointing to the specific device the attestation report is referring to.
createdAt	string	json:"createdAt"	The string identifier stores the creation date (e.g., timestamp). This feature allows for intricate searches on the ledger that rely on the date of creation.
listOfAttributes	[] string	json:" listofattributes"	This field specifies the list of access attributes that a given device or entity must possess to access and edit this specific data structure from the DLT.
Result	bool	json:" result"	Represents the outcome of the attestation, which might be either "pass" or "fail" based on the success or failure of the attestation.
AttestationPublicKeys	AttestationPKI	json:"attestationPublicKeys"	An AttestationPKI struct, which contains the DAA credentials of device and enclaves that responsible to create the attestation
Signature	string	json:" signature"	Signature of the medical device.

DBpointer	string	json:" DBPointer"	Pointer to off-chain. When an attestation is applied to a device, the result is a series of memory addresses that are stored in an off-chain data storage. This pointer is constructed to establish a connection with this data storage.
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Table 23 Device-level ATL Data Structure

Name	Data Type	JSON Schema	Description
TrustLvIValue	[] string	json:" trustLvIValue "	Indicates the trust opinion calculation derived by the Trust-level Expression Engine of the TAF for the target device trust model.
Signature	[] string	json:" signature"	This is the signature of TAF component.
DBpointer	[] string	json:" DBPointer"	Indicates the Off-chain Data Storage pointer of the evidence upon which the trust level is generated.

Table 24 Domain-level ATL Data Structure

Name	Data Type	JSON Schema	Description
TrustLvIValue	[] string	json:" trustLvIValue "	Indicates the trust opinion calculation of the domain based on fusion of trust opinions of each one of the domain's medical devices. More details on the trust methodology are provided in D3.2 [8].
Signature	[] string	json:" signature"	This is the signature of TAF component.
DBpointer	[][] string	json:" DBPointer"	Indicates the Off-chain Data Storage pointers of the evidence upon which the trust level is generated for all the devices belonging to the domain.

Table 25 Device-level Trust Policy Data Structure

Name	Data Type	JSON Schema	Description
DeviceID	string	json:" DeviceID"	This represents the medical device (e.g., CMD).
ATL	[] struct	json:" actualtrustlevel"	The Actual Trust Level (ATL) of the device that is evaluated periodically. Is derived from the computation based on the trustworthiness evidence of device to be

			determined if the device meets the requirements of the RTL.
RTL	[] integer	json:"requiredtrustlevel"	The Required Trust Level (RTL) is a baseline of the trust level that a CMD device needs to exhibit to be deemed trustworthy. This translates to an evaluation of the runtime ATL against this RTL. This is calculated as part of the Risk Assessment considering the device-specific threats and vulnerabilities from the manufacturer. Is a measure of the trustworthiness of the device before uploading the trustworthiness evidence to the Blockchain, to perform the runtime assessment.
TrustModel	[] string	json:"trustmodel"	Represents the type of data each device generates (e.g., OS, SW stack etc.) necessary for evaluating the trust level of the device.
ListOfTrustProperties	[] string	json:"listoftrustproperties"	An array of strings generated by TAF representing the trust opinion assessment (e.g. trust properties) for the specific device (e.g., integrity, confidentiality, etc.).
ListOfTrustSource	[] string	json:"listoftrustsource"	The type of evidences we need to monitor such as attestation evidence or AI-based anomaly detection evidence.
Periodicity	integer	json:"periodicity"	The frequency of retrieving the trustworthiness evidence from the device in a synchronous-based monitoring.
eMUDPointer	[] string	json:"eMUDPointer"	A string identifier pointing to the manufacturer's Device-level eMUD.
CCPointer	[] string	json:"CCPointer"	A string identifier pointing to the list of Device-level CCs generated by the specific policy.
ListOfAccessAttributes	[] string	json:"accessAttributes"	Set of access properties.
Signature	[] string	json:"signature"	This is the signature of Domain Manager.

Table 26 Domain-level Trust Policy Data Structure

Name	Data Type	JSON Schema	Description
DomainID	string	json:"DomainID"	This represents the Domain.
ListOfDeviceID	[] string	json:"LostOfDeviceID"	An array of strings that is calculated automatically based on the Device IDs as inherited by the Device-level Trust Policy of the devices enrolled in the domain.

ATL	[] struct	json:" actualtrustlevel"	The Actual Trust Level (ATL) is derived from the computation based on the trustworthiness evidence of services to be determined if the container of services meets the requirements of the RTL.
RTL	[] struct	json:" requiredtrustlevel"	The Required Trust Level (RTL) is a baseline of the trust level that a CMD domain needs to exhibit to be deemed trustworthy. This translates to an evaluation of the runtime ATL against this RTL. This is calculated as part of the Risk Assessment considering the device-specific threats and vulnerabilities from the manufacturer, inherited by the Device-level Trust Policy, and enriched with additional attack vectors (e.g., threats and vulnerabilities) emerged during onboarding in the domain.
TrustModel	[] string	json:" trustmodel"	An array that captures the medical devices relationships of the domain that need to be established and we need to assess the trust level. It also inherits the types of data that each device generates. The trust models for all the use cases are defined in D3.2 [8].
ListOfTrustProperties	[] string	json:" listoftrustproperties"	An inherited list of strings concatenated by the comprised devices of the specific domain.
ListOfTrustSource	[] string	json:" listoftrustsource"	The type of evidence we need to monitor such as attestation evidence or AI-based anomaly detection evidence.
Periodicity	integer	json:" periodicity"	Periodicity refers to the frequency at which the Domain Manager decides to request and collect trustworthiness evidence.
eMUDPointer	[] string	json:" eMUDPointer"	A string identifier pointing to the Domain-level eMUD.
CCPointer	[] string	json:" CCPointer"	A string identifier pointing to the list of Domain-level CCs generated by the specific policy.
ListOfAttributes	[] string	json:" listofattributes"	This field specifies the list of attributes that a given device or entity must possess to access and edit this specific data structure from the DLT.

Table 27 Device/Domain CC Data Structure

Name	Data Type	JSON Schema	Description
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ID	string	json:" ID"	This represents either the device or domain. (e.g., DeviceID or DomainID)
CC	string	json:" CC"	This is a W3C Verifiable Presentation based on trustworthiness certificate issued by the TAF for the list of trust properties of interest defined in associated trust policy. More details are provided in D4.2 [7].

Table 28 Domain eMUD Data Structure

Name	Data Type	JSON Schema	Description
DeviceID	string	json:" DeviceID"	This represents the medical device (e.g., CMD).
DomainID	string	json:" DomainID"	This represents the Domain.
swStack	[] string	json:" swStack"	It includes the SW, FW and OS versions of the device.
sysChars	[] string	json:" sysChars"	Represents the system characteristics of the device.
cryptoCap	[] string	json:" cryptoCap"	Represents the crypto capabilities of the device.
threats	[] string	json:" threats"	List of vulnerabilities and weakness identified by the manufacturer, enriched with the potential attack vectors of the domain identified by the risk assessment.
mitigation	[] string	json:" mitigation"	List of mitigations identified by the manufacturer, enriched with the potential mitigation actions relevant the attack vectors of the domain.
policyHashses	[] string	json:" mitigation"	Reference configuration values for all the binaries comprises the SW stack based on which the key restriction usage policies (e.g., key policy hashes) are created. Based on these policies the attestation key is created during the onboarding of the specific device in the domain.

Table 29 Threat Intelligence (STIX 2)

Name	Data Type	JSON Schema	Description
type	string	json:" type"	The value of this property MUST be campaign.
id	string	json:" id"	A name used to identify the Campaign.

spec_version	string	json:" spec_version"	A description that provides more details and context about the Campaign, potentially including its purpose and its key characteristics.
created	string	json:" created"	The string identifier stores the creation date (e.g., timestamp).
modified	string	json:" modified"	The string identifier stores the modification date (e.g., timestamp).
name	string	json:" name"	The string identifier stores the name.
description	string	json:" description"	A description that provides more details and context about the identified threat.

5.4 Smart Contract Management mediated through SCB

SCB plays a crucial role in facilitating the secure and efficient management, deployment, and execution of smart contracts. Acting as a **trusted intermediary between Blockchain smart contracts and external data sources**, SCB enables smart contracts to interact with off-chain data. SCB involves the creation and composition of smart contracts that will manage data flows within the ENTRUST framework and represents the conceptual need to design and construct various types of smart contracts tailored to support the different flows in the ENTRUST system. Such a design choice mediates the Blockchain transactions **removing the need for having a Blockchain client per entity** interacting with the Blockchain and in other words adopts the **chaincode-as-a-service approach**, through which the offered functions, applications, and smart contracts are provided to all the participating nodes “as-a-service” in an easily consumable way.

This concept is based on the gRPC framework, which enables all enrolled devices to directly call the services as local objects, and without the need to define and agree on a common language prior to any interaction. Chaincode itself can be considered as RPC-like service, enabling any device to be able to interact with this contract service irrespective of the type of programming language used since the generation of the appropriate code to be executed on the chaincode has been created on-the-fly. With this novel approach, it is feasible to run “chaincode-as-a-service”, providing the users the power to access, deploy and run chaincode instantly even outside the Blockchain network, taking of course all the measures related to the authorization of the users.

In general, the SCB serves as a trusted bridge in the data sharing process of ENTRUST Blockchain infrastructure. From an architecture perspective, the SCB is set inside the ENTRUST Blockchain framework as a Blockchain user. In this case, it will have its own Blockchain credentials (e.g., Blockchain public and private keys). It will mainly interact with the following components (see Figure 4). The SCB will work with the Blockchain Peer(s) to maintain effective ABAC on Blockchain data by using smart contracts and the MSP mechanism.

Figure 4: Overview of the Interactions between SCB and ENTRUST Components

Upon deployment, developers initialize the SCB contracts to manage interactions with end-users or other on-chain entities. The data request lifecycle involves several key steps. A user or entity initiates a data request through the SCB contracts, to processes the request by logging it and securely interacting with external data sources to fetch the requested information. The system incorporates various contract management functions, including upgrade and maintenance, suspension and restart, and withdrawal of funds, ensuring efficient operation and economic sustainability.

In what follows, we expand on the main functionalities supported by the SCB.

SCB-F1 - First of all, the SCB is able to manage the creation and deployment of policies (e.g., attestation or SW/FW update) based on smart contracts. The SCB will act as a trusted operator converting the policy into smart contract logic (chain code). The resulting smart contract will be finally deployed on the ledger.

SCB-F2 - The second functionality supported by the SCB is the ABAC mechanism. The ABAC is used to guarantee that internal or external entities who wish to get access to the Blockchain recorded data should be authenticated and verified via their attributes. Original attributes of devices or entities will be verified during enrolment. If the new devices would like to enrol to the Blockchain network, they forward the attributes to the SCB for verification. Also, the Hyperledger Fabric’s MSP mechanism allows Blockchain users’ credentials to be stored on Blockchain Peer(s), so that the Peer(s) can always verify the identities of users. For example, after receiving a transaction signed by a device, a Peer can use the device’s public key to verify the signature so as to confirm if the Peer should reject or accept the transaction request.

SCB-F3 - Another important and innovative feature provided by the SCB is the Off-Chain Data Storage. After receiving raw data to be stored on the ledger, the SCB will send this data to the

Off-Chain Data Storage due to each size. The Off-Chain Data Storage will store the data in encrypted form (using ABE) and return the corresponding pointer. Then, the SCB will store the pointer on the ledger. While the internal entities request to access the data on the ledger, their credentials can be checked via ABAC before accessing them.

6 Tracer – Connected Medical Devices State Monitoring

In the realm of Connected Medical Devices (CMDs), ensuring security and safety is paramount. Tracing techniques are vital tools for monitoring these devices, detecting anomalies, and identifying potential vulnerabilities. In the ENTRUST framework, tracing capabilities are specifically employed to monitor the values of trust properties of CMDs, verifying that the device remains in a trustworthy state. These techniques allow for a deep understanding of the system's behavior and the ability to trace different trust attributes, which is crucial for maintaining the integrity and reliability of CMDs. Effective tracing can significantly enhance the security posture of connected devices by providing continuous trust assessment, making it an indispensable part of modern security frameworks.

Software Tracing (SW Tracing): Software tracing involves instrumenting code with logging statements or utilizing tracing libraries to monitor the execution of software. This method provides detailed insights into the software's behavior at runtime. One of the primary advantages of software tracing is its high granularity, allowing for a comprehensive view of internal processes. Additionally, it is flexible and easily customizable to capture specific events or data points, making it accessible for developers to implement and adjust without requiring specialized hardware. However, software tracing can significantly impact system performance, especially if extensive logging is enabled, and it is limited in its visibility to hardware-level issues.

Hardware Tracing (HW Tracing): Hardware tracing uses specialized hardware components to monitor and record the activity of other hardware within a system. This method is often used for low-level analysis of processor behavior, memory accesses, and other hardware interactions. The primary advantage of hardware tracing is its low overhead, typically introducing minimal performance impact. It also offers comprehensive visibility, capturing events at the hardware level that software tracing cannot access, and is suitable for real-time monitoring. However, hardware tracing requires specialized hardware and expertise to set up and interpret, and it can be expensive due to the need for additional hardware components.

Hardware-assisted Software Tracing: This technique combines software tracing with hardware support to improve performance and accuracy. It leverages hardware features to facilitate efficient data collection without the high overhead of pure software tracing. This balanced approach reduces the performance impact and enhances accuracy by combining the strengths of both hardware and software tracing. However, it requires specific hardware features not available in all systems and is more complex to set up than pure software or hardware tracing.

Out-of-Band Tracing: Out-of-band tracing involves collecting tracing data through a separate channel, independent of the main system operations. This method ensures that tracing does not interfere with the system's performance. It offers the advantage of no impact on the main operations and high reliability, as tracing data is collected independently, reducing the risk of missing critical events. However, out-of-band tracing requires additional infrastructure and potentially extra hardware for data collection, making it complex to set up and maintain.

6.1 Extended Berkeley Packet Filter (eBPF)

eBPF is a highly flexible and powerful tracing technology that allows developers to write custom programs running in the Linux kernel. It can trace events, monitor system performance, and enhance security by filtering and analysing network traffic. eBPF's primary advantages include high efficiency and minimal performance overhead, as it runs within the kernel. Its programmability allows for custom tracing solutions tailored to specific needs, and its versatility makes it useful for a wide range of tracing and monitoring tasks. Furthermore, eBPF ensures that

tracing programs are verified and safe to execute in the kernel context. However, writing effective eBPF programs requires expertise, and it is specific to the Linux operating system, limiting its applicability to other environments.

In essence, eBPF programs are small, user-defined bytecode programs that run in the kernel, written in a restricted C-like language and compiled into bytecode. The eBPF VM, a lightweight VM embedded in the Linux kernel, executes this bytecode, providing a secure execution environment for eBPF programs. Efficient data structures known as eBPF maps are used to store data shared between eBPF programs and user-space applications. These maps can hold various types of data, including arrays, hash tables, and ring buffers. Hooks are points in the kernel where eBPF programs can be attached, available for various subsystems such as network sockets, system calls, and tracepoints.

The operation flow of eBPF begins with program loading. eBPF programs are typically written in a high-level language like C and then compiled into eBPF bytecode using the LLVM compiler. The bytecode is then loaded into the kernel using the `bpf()` system call, which checks the program's validity and safety before loading it into the eBPF VM. A crucial part of eBPF operation is the verification step, where the eBPF verifier checks the bytecode for safety and correctness. This ensures the program does not contain any loops (to prevent infinite execution) and adheres to strict constraints to avoid compromising kernel stability. The verifier also ensures the program does not perform any unsafe operations, such as accessing invalid memory or performing illegal instructions. Once verified and loaded, eBPF programs are attached to specific hooks within the kernel, determining the context in which the eBPF program will run, such as network packet processing, system call execution, or performance monitoring. For example, an eBPF program can be attached to a network socket to inspect and modify packets as they are received or transmitted. When the conditions specified by the hook are met, the eBPF VM executes the attached eBPF program. During execution, the program can perform various operations, such as reading and writing to eBPF maps, modifying packet data, or logging information for further analysis. eBPF programs often interact with user-space applications through eBPF maps. User-space applications can read from and write to these maps using the `bpf()` system call, enabling dynamic data exchange and configuration. This interaction allows for real-time monitoring and analysis of kernel events, as well as dynamic adjustments based on user-space feedback.

Figure 5: eBPF and BCC Integration in the Linux Kernel for Process Monitoring

Error! Reference source not found. ¹⁹ illustrates the integration of eBPF and BCC within the Linux Kernel for process monitoring. The process begins with an eBPF program, often written in Python, which is loaded into the BCC. The BCC uses system calls to interface with the Linux Kernel, where the eBPF verifier checks the safety and correctness of the eBPF program. Once verified, the eBPF JIT compiler translates the program into native machine code for execution. eBPF maps are used to store and share data between the kernel and user space processes. eBPF programs can be attached to various points in the kernel, such as syscalls, sockets, and TCP/IP stack, to monitor and manipulate the behavior of processes. The data collected by eBPF programs can be accessed by user space applications to monitor system performance and security in real-time.

In the context of CMDs, eBPF can be utilized for various purposes. For network security, eBPF can monitor and filter network traffic to detect and prevent malicious activities, thereby helping to maintain the integrity and reliability of communications between CMDs. For performance monitoring, eBPF can trace system calls and kernel functions to monitor performance and detect anomalies, helping to maintain the reliability and efficiency of CMDs. Additionally, eBPF allows for real-time analysis of system behavior, enabling prompt responses to security incidents and operational issues. By leveraging the internal capabilities of eBPF, Entrust can achieve a high level of security, performance, and flexibility in monitoring and managing CMDs, ensuring their safe and reliable operation within a zero-trust framework. Furthermore, eBPF's ability to collect detailed attestation evidence supports the attestation schemes used in Entrust, allowing for the continuous evaluation of trust properties and verification of the device's trustworthiness.

6.2 eBPF in ENTRUST

Entrust has chosen eBPF as its primary tracing technique for CMDs for several compelling reasons. Firstly, eBPF programs run in the kernel, providing high efficiency and minimal performance impact, which is crucial for real-time medical devices where performance and responsiveness are critical. Secondly, eBPF's programmability allows for custom tracing solutions that can be tailored to the specific needs of CMDs, enabling detailed monitoring and analysis without significant system modifications. Thirdly, eBPF ensures that tracing programs are verified and safe to execute within the kernel, reducing the risk of introducing vulnerabilities or instability in the system. Additionally, eBPF can monitor a wide range of system activities, from network traffic to system calls, providing a comprehensive view of the system's behavior and potential security issues. The ability to deploy eBPF programs dynamically allows for scalable and adaptive monitoring solutions that can evolve with the system's requirements. By leveraging eBPF, Entrust aims to ensure the secure and safe design of CMDs, adhering to Zero Trust principles by continuously verifying the integrity and trustworthiness of each component and activity within the system, and never assuming trust based on location or previous interactions. This approach provides robust, efficient, and flexible tracing capabilities that are essential for maintaining the high security and reliability standards required in medical environments.

Figure 6 illustrates the tracing and attestation process flow within the ENTRUST framework, involving various components that ensure the trustworthiness and security of CMDs. The process is divided between the Verifier and Prover entities, each playing distinct roles in the attestation

¹⁹ <https://ebpf.io/>

lifecycle. In the Prover section, the Trust Agent initiates the attestation process to verify the integrity and trustworthiness of the device. The Tracer collects and sends runtime data and security claims to the Attestation Agent as part of this process. In the Verifier section, the Attestation Agent receives data from the Tracer and executes the attestation logic. Based on the results, it sends back an attestation result or requests raw traces if further analysis is needed. The Entrust Blockchain stores the attestation results and raw traces, ensuring the integrity and availability of the data, thus supporting transparency and auditability of the attestation process. The Digital Twin simulates the CMD's operations and requests raw traces from the Entrust Blockchain for further analysis, especially in cases where anomalies are detected, or additional verification is required. Figure 6 highlights the interactions between these components, ensuring that the CMDs maintain a high level of security and trustworthiness through continuous monitoring and verification. Components classified as Trusted are marked in green, while the Untrusted component is marked in red, indicating the trust state during the attestation process.

Figure 6: Tracing Process Flow for CMDs

The need for the tracer to provide data to the TAF and, if necessary, to the Digital Twin, stems from the overarching goal of ensuring the trustworthiness and security of CMDs throughout their operational lifecycle. The tracer serves as a critical component in the ENTRUST framework by collecting and providing essential runtime data and security claims.

The TAF utilizes the data provided by the tracer to calculate the ATL of CMDs. This involves:

1. **Trust Evidence Collection:** The tracer gathers runtime information and security claims from CMDs, which are then encrypted and sent to the attestation agent. This process is crucial for verifying the integrity and authenticity of the data collected from the devices.
2. **Trust Model Management:** The TAF incorporates this data to manage and update the trust models, ensuring that the ATL of each device is accurately assessed against the

RTL. The ATL calculation is based on the trust attributes specified in the Trust Model, which includes data collected by the tracer. The Trust Properties are evaluated based on the information collected by the corresponding Trust Sources. One such Trust Source is the attestation, in the context of which the tracer collects trustworthiness evidence.

3. **Continuous Monitoring and Assessment:** The TAF continuously assesses the trustworthiness of CMDs by comparing the ATL with the RTL. If the ATL is lower than the RTL, it indicates a potential risk, prompting the need for further actions such as secure software updates or additional attestation measures through the digital twins.

The Digital Twin leverages the data provided by the tracer for more advanced simulation and analysis:

1. **Real-time Monitoring and Simulation:** The Digital Twin creates a dynamic, virtual representation of CMDs, enabling real-time monitoring and simulation of cyber threats. This allows for proactive identification and mitigation of vulnerabilities within a controlled environment.
2. **Intrusion and Misbehavior Detection:** In cases where the ATL is found to be below the RTL, the Digital Twin can emulate the attack paths and analyse the deviations from expected behavior. This facilitates AI-based intrusion detection and helps in identifying and responding to potential security breaches promptly .
3. **Security Design and Optimization:** By continuously feeding data from the tracer into the Digital Twin, the system can perform ongoing learning and adaptation, ensuring that security measures remain effective against evolving threats. This iterative process enhances the overall resilience and trustworthiness of the CMD infrastructure.

The integration of tracer data into the TAF and the Digital Twin is fundamental to maintaining a robust security posture for CMDs. It ensures continuous trust assessment, real-time monitoring, and proactive security management, thereby safeguarding patient safety and the integrity of medical systems.

6.3 Data Structure

In the ENTRUST framework, data structure plays a crucial role in ensuring the integrity and trustworthiness of CMDs. This section outlines the static and runtime properties that form the baseline for the attestation process. The data collected and analysed by the tracers provide essential evidence to support the trust assessment and anomaly detection mechanisms implemented by the TAF and the AI-based systems.

6.3.1 Static Properties: Secure Boot

Secure boot is a crucial static property that ensures the integrity of the software running on CMDs from the moment they are powered on. Secure boot verifies that the firmware and software have not been tampered with and are from a trusted source. This process involves cryptographic validation of the bootloader, operating system, and application software before they are executed. The tracer collects data on the boot sequence, recording cryptographic signatures and verification steps to ensure that only authenticated code runs on the device. This data structure typically includes the following:

- **Boot Sequence Logs:** Records of each step in the boot process, including timestamps and status messages.

- **Cryptographic Signatures:** Hashes and digital signatures of boot components for verification purposes.
- **Verification Results:** Outcomes of each verification step, indicating whether the component is trusted or flagged as potentially compromised.

Using this collected data, the system can generate attestation reports that provide evidence of the secure boot process. These reports can be used to prove to external auditors or other devices that the CMD has booted securely and is running trusted software.

6.3.2 Runtime Properties: Runtime Configuration Integrity and Control Flow Integrity

Runtime Configuration Integrity: Maintaining the integrity of the runtime configuration is essential for ensuring that CMDs operate as intended. Tracers monitor the configuration settings of the device during its operation, detecting any unauthorized changes that could indicate a security breach or malfunction. The data structure for runtime configuration integrity typically includes:

- **Configuration Snapshots:** Periodic captures of the current configuration settings, including system parameters and security policies.
- **Change Logs:** Detailed records of any modifications to the configuration, including the source of the change and the new values.
- **Integrity Checksums:** Hashes of configuration files and settings to detect unauthorized alterations.

By analyzing this data, the system can detect and respond to configuration anomalies, triggering alerts or automatic remediation actions to restore the original settings.

Runtime Control Flow Integrity: Control flow integrity (CFI) ensures that the execution flow of a program follows its intended path, preventing attacks that hijack the control flow, such as buffer overflows or code injection. Tracers collect data on the execution flow of software running on CMDs, monitoring function calls and control transfers to ensure they adhere to the expected control flow graph (CFG). The data structure for CFI typically includes:

- **Execution Trace Logs:** Records of executed instructions, function calls, and control transfers, including their addresses and timestamps.
- **Control Flow Graphs:** Pre-computed graphs representing the legitimate control flows of the software.
- **Anomaly Reports:** Logs of detected deviations from the expected control flow, indicating potential security violations.

This data helps in constructing a detailed view of the program's execution, enabling the detection of control flow attacks and providing evidence for attestation reports.

6.3.3 Baseline to Attestation Process

To create a baseline for the attestation process, the tracer collects and analyzes data during the normal, secure operation of the CMD. This baseline includes:

- **Secure Boot Records:** Logs and verification results from the secure boot process.
- **Configuration Snapshots and Change Logs:** Records of the initial and subsequent configuration settings.

- **Control Flow Graphs and Execution Traces:** Documentation of the intended control flows and actual execution traces during normal operation.

Using this baseline, the attestation process involves continuously monitoring and comparing the current state of the device against the established baseline. Any deviations or anomalies are flagged for further analysis. The attestation process includes the following steps:

- **Data Collection:** Continuous gathering of runtime data, including boot sequences, configuration settings, and execution flows.
- **Integrity Verification:** Checking the collected data against the baseline to detect unauthorized changes or anomalies.
- **Anomaly Detection:** Identifying and logging any deviations from the expected behaviour, triggering alerts or remediation actions.
- **Attestation Reporting:** Generating reports that summarize the integrity and security status of the CMD, based on the collected and analysed data.

By leveraging these detailed data structures and the attestation process, Entrust can ensure the static and runtime integrity of CMDs, providing robust security assurances and maintaining trust in the connected medical ecosystem.

6.4 High-end devices

Figure 7: ENTRUST tracer in a high-end device

The tracer on high-end devices, such as those based on Raspberry Pi platforms, utilizes advanced tracing and monitoring technologies to provide comprehensive system visibility and security, given the fact that they are able to employ Linux-dependant tools. These devices leverage eBPF technology, and more specifically tools from the BCC, along with a custom script to achieve detailed monitoring and analysis. In essence, the tracer employs eBPF, which allows the execution of user-defined programs within the Linux kernel safely and efficiently. This enables the tracer to capture and analyse various system events with minimal performance overhead. Also, with the use of eBPF, the tracer can monitor system calls, network packets, and kernel-level events in real time. This provides deep insights into system behavior and performance. The custom scripts are utilized to extend the capabilities of eBPF-based tracing, as they are tailored to capture custom metrics and execute specific monitoring tasks depending on the required data at any given time. These scripts allow for flexibility in monitoring and can be adapted to meet the unique needs of the device and its operational environment.

Figure 7 depicts the architecture of the ENTRUST TCB for high-end devices, illustrating the interactions between various trusted and untrusted components within the system. At the hardware level, the high-end device is equipped with a PUF and a Secure Bootloader, ensuring

that the device starts with verified and trusted firmware. Above the hardware, the operating system includes eBPF capabilities for advanced monitoring and tracing.

Within the ENTRUST-TCB, the Trusted OS operates alongside several critical components:

- **Attestation Agent:** Verifies the integrity and trustworthiness of the device based on data from the Tracer.
- **Blockchain Wallet:** Stores verifiable credentials and manages cryptographic keys and interacts with Blockchain services to record attestation results.
- **Tracer:** Utilizes eBPF to monitor runtime activities and gather essential data for trust assessment.
- **Verifiable Credentials:** Issuance and verification of credentials to ensure secure interactions are taking place in the TCB.

Untrusted components, such as the application (APP) and the Trust Agent, interact with the Tracer to initiate the attestation process. The Tracer then provides the collected data to the Attestation Agent within the ENTRUST-TCB. The Trust Agent operates within the untrusted OS environment, while the Tracer ensures that only authenticated and verified data is processed for attestation.

6.4.1 BCC (type of data)

The BPF Compiler Collection (BCC) is an advanced framework that significantly enhances the capabilities of Linux system monitoring and tracing. BCC leverages the power of eBPF (Extended Berkeley Packet Filter) technology, which allows user-defined programs to execute directly within the Linux kernel in a safe and efficient manner. This deep integration with the kernel provides unparalleled visibility into system operations, enabling detailed monitoring and analysis with minimal performance overhead. BCC includes a comprehensive suite of pre-built tools designed to monitor various system aspects such as system calls, network packets, CPU usage, memory allocation, and other kernel-level events in real time. These tools are indispensable for performance analysis, system troubleshooting, and security auditing.

BCC's flexibility is further enhanced by its support for custom scripting. With bindings for Python and Lua, developers can easily extend BCC's functionality by writing custom scripts that tailor the monitoring process to their specific needs. This allows for the capture of custom metrics, execution of specialized monitoring tasks, and detailed analysis tailored to unique operational requirements. The ability to create these custom scripts makes BCC highly adaptable, suitable for a wide range of use cases from simple monitoring tasks to complex performance diagnostics and security audits. Additionally, BCC facilitates dynamic tracing, allowing developers and system administrators to insert probes into running systems without needing to restart or recompile the kernel. This dynamic capability is crucial for minimizing downtime and maintaining system stability while performing in-depth analysis. BCC's tools, such as opensnoop, execsnoop, and tcplife, among others, provide ready-to-use, powerful tracing functions that cover a broad spectrum of monitoring needs.

In essence, BCC combines the efficiency of eBPF with a user-friendly interface and scripting support, making it an indispensable toolkit for those seeking granular insights into Linux system behavior. Its ability to perform detailed and efficient monitoring and tracing with minimal impact on system performance positions BCC as a crucial resource for optimizing and securing Linux environments.

6.4.1.1 Performance Monitoring

In the context of BCC, the following tools are crucial for performance monitoring:

- **biolatency-bpfcc** (Runtime): This tool measures block device I/O latency. It helps in identifying latency issues related to disk operations, which is essential for diagnosing performance bottlenecks in storage systems. By providing detailed latency metrics, system administrators can pinpoint specific devices or workloads causing delays.
- **biotop-bpfcc** (Runtime): Displays top block device I/O by process. This tool allows users to see which processes are generating the most I/O load on block devices. It is useful for understanding which applications or processes are responsible for heavy disk usage, aiding in resource management and optimization.
- **biosnoop-bpfcc** (Runtime): Traces block device I/O. This tool provides a detailed trace of I/O operations on block devices, offering insights into the sequence and nature of I/O requests. It is particularly useful for debugging and analysing the behavior of applications with intensive I/O operations.
- **cpudist-bpfcc** (Runtime): Shows CPU time distribution. This tool helps in understanding how CPU time is distributed across different tasks and processes. It is essential for performance tuning and identifying CPU-bound workloads.
- **execsnoop-bpfcc** (Runtime): Traces process execution. By monitoring process execution, this tool helps in tracking process creation and command execution, providing valuable information for security auditing and performance analysis.
- **funccount-bpfcc** (Static): Counts function calls in kernel or user programs. This tool is used to measure the frequency of function calls, which can help in identifying hotspots in code and understanding the behavior of applications at the function level.
- **funclatency-bpfcc** (Runtime): Measures function call latency. It provides insights into the time taken by specific function calls, which is useful for performance profiling and optimizing critical code paths.
- **offcputime-bpfcc** (Runtime): Shows off-CPU time by kernel stack trace. This tool measures the time processes spend waiting (off-CPU), which is crucial for identifying performance issues related to resource contention, I/O wait times, and scheduling delays.
- **runqlat-bpfcc** (Runtime): Measures scheduler run queue latency. This tool helps in understanding the latency introduced by the scheduler's run queue, which affects how quickly processes get CPU time. It is important for tuning scheduler performance and ensuring efficient CPU utilization.

6.4.1.2 Security Monitoring

- **capable-bpfcc (static)**: Traces security capability checks. This tool helps in monitoring and auditing the use of Linux capabilities, which are a set of fine-grained permissions that can be granted to processes. It ensures that only authorized processes are executing actions that require specific capabilities, enhancing security monitoring.
- **execsnoop-bpfcc** (Runtime): Monitors process execution for security auditing. This tool is crucial for tracking process creation and execution, providing detailed information about which commands are being run. It helps in identifying unauthorized or suspicious activities, making it an essential tool for security auditing.

- **killsnoop-bpfcc** (Runtime): Monitors signal sending for security auditing. This tool tracks the sending of signals between processes, which is important for detecting attempts to terminate or manipulate processes. It aids in identifying malicious activities such as process hijacking or unauthorized termination of critical services.
- **opensnoop-bpfcc** (Runtime): Traces open() syscalls to monitor file access. By tracking file open operations, this tool provides insights into which files are being accessed, when, and by which processes. It is valuable for detecting unauthorized access to sensitive files and for compliance auditing.
- **bindsnoop-bpfcc** (Runtime): Monitors bind() syscall to see what addresses/ports are being bound on. This tool helps in tracking network services that are being started and the addresses/ports they are binding to. It is essential for detecting unauthorized network services and potential security breaches.

6.4.1.3 Network Monitoring

- **tcpconnect-bpfcc** (Runtime): Traces active TCP connections. This tool monitors outgoing TCP connections, providing information on which processes are initiating connections. It is useful for detecting unauthorized or suspicious network activities.
- **tcpaccept-bpfcc** (Runtime): Traces passive TCP connections. By tracking incoming TCP connections, this tool helps in monitoring which services are accepting connections and from where. It aids in identifying potential intrusion attempts or unauthorized access.
- **tcplife-bpfcc** (Runtime): Shows the lifespan of TCP connections. This tool provides insights into the duration of TCP connections, helping to identify long-lived connections that might be indicative of data exfiltration or persistent threats.
- **tcpretrans-bpfcc** (Runtime): Monitors TCP retransmits. This tool helps in detecting network issues by tracking TCP packet retransmissions, which can indicate network congestion, faulty connections, or potential security attacks like SYN flooding.
- **netqtop-bpfcc** (Runtime): Analyses traffic in network interfaces and displays statistics about packets in the queues of these interfaces. This tool provides a detailed view of network traffic, helping in the analysis of network performance and detection of anomalies.

6.4.1.4 Filesystem Monitoring

- **filelife-bpfcc** (Runtime): Monitors the lifespan of files. This tool tracks the creation and deletion of files, providing insights into temporary files and their usage patterns. Although it is not currently working, it would be useful for detecting unauthorized file manipulations.
- **fileslower-bpfcc** (Runtime): Traces slow file operations. This tool identifies slow file operations, helping to diagnose performance issues related to the filesystem and pinpoint bottlenecks.
- **ext4dist-bpfcc** (Runtime): Shows the distribution of ext4 file operation latencies. This tool provides detailed latency metrics for ext4 filesystems, aiding in the analysis of filesystem performance and detection of issues.
- **btrfsdist-bpfcc** (Runtime): Shows latency distribution for Btrfs file operations. Although it is not currently working due to kernel build differences, it would help in understanding the performance characteristics of Btrfs filesystems.

6.4.1.5 Database Monitoring

- **dbslower-bpfcc** (Runtime): Traces slow database queries. This tool helps in identifying slow queries that may be affecting database performance, enabling optimization and tuning of database operations.
- **dbstat-bpfcc** (Runtime): Provides statistics on database operations. This tool offers a broad overview of database activities, helping in monitoring and maintaining database performance and identifying potential issues.

6.4.1.6 System Calls and Kernel Monitoring

- **argdist-bpfcc** (Static): Summarizes function argument values. This tool provides aggregated statistics on function argument values, which is useful for understanding the behavior and usage patterns of system calls and functions.
- **biosnoop-bpfcc** (Runtime): Monitors block I/O requests. This tool helps in tracking block I/O operations, providing insights into disk activity and performance.
- **cachestat-bpfcc** (Runtime): Monitors cache hit/miss ratios. This tool provides metrics on cache performance, helping to optimize memory usage and improve system performance.
- **cachetop-bpfcc** (Runtime): Shows top cache users in real-time. This tool identifies processes that are heavily using the cache, helping to detect inefficient cache usage and potential performance issues.
- **funccount-bpfcc** (Static): Counts function calls in the kernel. This tool provides a count of function calls, helping to identify hotspots in kernel code and understand system behavior at a low level.
- **funcslower-bpfcc** (Runtime): Traces slow kernel functions. This tool identifies kernel functions that are taking a long time to execute, which is crucial for diagnosing performance bottlenecks in the kernel.

6.5 Low-end devices

For low-end devices, the tracer is designed to provide essential system visibility and security while operating within the limited resources available. In the ENTRUST framework, there is a clear distinction between high-end and low-end devices based on their use cases and capabilities. High-end devices, such as gateways, are more powerful and capable of running advanced monitoring and tracing tools like eBPF. These devices serve as central hubs that manage and secure communications for a network of connected devices. On the other hand, low-end devices, such as wearables connected to the gateway, have limited computational and memory resources. These low-end devices rely on lightweight monitoring solutions and secure communication protocols to ensure their integrity and trustworthiness without compromising performance. The tracer for low-end devices must therefore be optimized to operate efficiently within these constraints while still providing crucial data for the overall security and trust management framework.

These devices typically utilize Zephyr RTOS, which makes it possible to run Segger SystemView, custom scripts, and set up secure boot mechanisms for effective system monitoring and analysis. Zephyr RTOS, a scalable and lightweight real-time operating system, efficiently manages the device's resources and provides a reliable platform for running the tracer. Segger SystemView is a real-time recording and visualization tool that offers insightful tracing capabilities without

imposing significant performance overhead, allowing developers to monitor system behavior, analyse performance, and identify issues efficiently. Secure boot ensures that the device starts up using only trusted software, enhancing the security of the system from the moment it powers on. Custom scripts are employed to automate specific monitoring tasks and capture necessary data tailored to the device's operational needs. These scripts provide flexibility and can be adapted to meet the unique requirements of the device and its environment. This approach ensures that low-end devices maintain a balance between performance and visibility, allowing for effective monitoring and management within their operational limits. For developing purposes, we use the Nordic nRF52840 Development Kit to ensure that the tracer functions optimally within the constraints of low-end devices. This approach ensures that low-end devices maintain a balance between performance and visibility, allowing for effective monitoring and management within their operational limits.

Figure 8: Static and Runtime Properties Collection on Low-end devices

Figure 8 illustrates the ENTRUST framework for collecting and attesting static and runtime properties of CMDs, particularly focusing on a baremetal device based on the Nordic nRF52840 Development Kit. The process ensures the integrity and trustworthiness of the devices through continuous monitoring and verification. The baremetal device (Nordic nRF52840 DK) forms the base hardware platform for the CMDs. It utilizes MCUBoot (Secure Bootloader) to ensure the device boots using only authenticated and authorized firmware. The Zephyr RTOS manages device operations. Within the ENTRUST pseudo-TCB, the Tracer component is responsible for collecting data. The Tracer monitors and collects both static and runtime properties of the CMD. Static properties include the secure boot sequence, which ensures the integrity of the device firmware. Runtime properties include CPU usage and memory usage, providing real-time insights into the device's performance. The Trust Agent interacts with the Tracer to initiate the attestation

process, operating within an untrusted application environment. The Attestation Agent receives data from the Tracer to perform the attestation process, ensuring the trustworthiness of the device. Components are classified as Trusted (marked in green) and Untrusted (marked in red), indicating their trust status within the framework. The flow of information from the Trust Agent to the Tracer and then to the Attestation Agent highlights the process of verifying and maintaining the security and reliability of the CMDs through the ENTRUST framework.

6.5.1 Segger SystemView

Segger SystemView is a powerful real-time recording and visualization tool specifically designed for embedded systems, making it an excellent choice for monitoring and tracing capabilities in our Zephyr-enabled nRF52840-based devices. These Nordic Semiconductor devices are widely used in various applications, including IoT, wearables, and medical devices, where performance and reliability are crucial. SystemView provides deep insights into the behavior and performance of embedded applications by capturing and visualizing system events with minimal overhead. This tool allows developers to monitor task execution, interrupts, and system events in real-time, facilitating thorough analysis and debugging of complex applications. For nRF52840 devices, which operate in resource-constrained environments, SystemView's low overhead ensures that it does not interfere significantly with system performance, allowing for accurate and reliable tracing.

One of the key advantages of SystemView is its ability to provide a detailed and comprehensive view of the system's runtime behavior. This capability is particularly beneficial for nRF52 and nRF53 series devices, as it helps understand the interactions and timing of various system components, leading to more efficient and optimized monitoring. SystemView's integration with the Zephyr RTOS enhances its utility by enabling us to gain granular insights into task scheduling, interrupt handling, and other kernel activities. This synergy allows for fine-tuning of system performance, identification of malicious behavior, and swift resolution of issues. Its ability to provide detailed system insights, low overhead, and seamless integration with Zephyr RTOS makes it invaluable for embedded system developers aiming to enhance performance and reliability.

Segger SystemView offers robust monitoring and tracing capabilities for embedded systems, particularly useful for Zephyr-enabled nRF52 and nRF53 devices. Through SystemView, developers can export two types of files that provide detailed insights into system behavior and performance:

6.5.1.1 Detailed Logs of Events Captured (Runtime)

This file contains comprehensive logs of the events recorded by the system, allowing for in-depth analysis of system activities. The attributes included are:

- **Sequencenum:** Sequential number of the event, providing an ordered timeline of events.
- **Timestamp:** Time at which the event occurred, formatted as "seconds nanoseconds", offering precise timing information.
- **Context:** The state of the system when the event was logged (e.g., Idle, ISR), helping to understand the system's status during each event.
- **Event:** Type of event that occurred (e.g., Start, Init, System Description), categorizing the nature of each event.
- **Detail:** Additional details about the event, providing context and specifics.
- **Timestampint:** Integer representation of the timestamp, useful for computational analysis.

- **Contextinint:** Integer representation of the input context, aiding in detailed state analysis.
- **Contextint:** Integer representation of the current context, showing the current state numerically.
- **Contextoutint:** Integer representation of the output context, indicating the resulting state after the event.
- **Eventint:** Integer code for the event, facilitating quick event type identification.
- **Eventoffset:** Offset position of the event in the log, helping in locating specific events.
- **Eventsize:** Size of the event data, indicating the amount of data associated with each event.
- **Eventdata:** Raw data associated with the event, providing raw metrics for in-depth analysis.

6.5.1.2 Summary of Thread and Context Execution Details (Runtime)

This file provides an overview of the execution details for threads and contexts, crucial for performance and efficiency analysis. The included attributes are:

- **Name:** Name of the thread or context (e.g., ISR 33, Scheduler), identifying the specific entity being monitored.
- **Type:** Type identifier for the context, categorizing the context type.
- **Stack Information:** Details about the stack usage, including size and memory address, crucial for memory management and debugging.
- **Activations:** Number of times the thread or context has been activated, indicating activity frequency.
- **Total Blocked Time:** Total time the thread was blocked, helping to identify bottlenecks.
- **Total Run Time:** Total time the thread was running, giving insights into its operational workload.
- **Time Interrupted:** Total time the thread was interrupted, important for understanding system preemptions.
- **CPU Load:** CPU load percentage for the thread, providing performance metrics.
- **Last Run Time:** Time taken during the last run of the thread, useful for recent performance evaluation.
- **Min Run Time:** Minimum run time observed, indicating the best-case performance scenario.
- **Max Run Time:** Maximum run time observed, indicating the worst-case performance scenario.
- **Min Blocked Time:** Minimum time the thread was blocked, showing the least delay encountered.

Max Blocked Time: Maximum time the thread was blocked, highlighting the most significant delays.

Run Time/s: Running time of the thread per second, offering a normalized performance metric.

Min Run Time/s: Minimum running time per second, providing the best-case execution rate.

- **Max Run Time/s:** Maximum running time per second, showing the peak execution rate.

6.5.2 Secure boot (Static)

Secure Boot ensures that an nRF52840 device boots using only software that is trusted by the device manufacturer. In the context of ENTRUST, the output of the Secure Boot process serves as a critical piece of trust evidence. The successful verification of firmware integrity during the boot process generates a cryptographic attestation, which is then collected by the tracer and used as part of the trustworthiness evidence. This evidence is forwarded to the Trust Assessment Framework (TAF), where it contributes to the calculation of the Actual Trust Level (ATL) of the device. By confirming that the device has booted with authenticated and untampered firmware, Secure Boot reinforces the trust model and ensures that the device starts in a secure and trustworthy state.

This process involves verifying the integrity and authenticity of the firmware before it is executed. Secure Boot works by performing a check against a cryptographic signature or a pre-approved hash of the firmware. The sequence of actions in Secure Boot includes:

Manufacturer's Role:

1. Sign Firmware with Private Key: The manufacturer signs the hashed firmware image using a private key.
2. Store Public Key on Device: The corresponding public key is stored on the device along with the signature.

Bootloader's Role:

1. Boot Device: Initiates the boot sequence.
2. Read Firmware from Memory: The bootloader reads the firmware image from the device memory.
3. Compute Hash of Firmware Image: The bootloader computes the hash of the read firmware image.
4. Decrypt Signature using Public Key: The bootloader uses the stored public key to decrypt the signature.
5. Retrieve Original Hash from Signature: The decrypted signature reveals the original hash value that was signed with the private key.
6. Compare Computed Hash with Decrypted Hash: The bootloader compares the newly computed hash with the decrypted original hash.
7. Verify and Boot: If the hashes match, the firmware is considered verified, and the bootloader proceeds to boot the device securely.
8. Halt Boot: If the hashes do not match, the bootloader halts the boot process to prevent untrusted firmware from executing.

Secure Booting with MCUBoot on nRF52840 Devices

Figure 9: Secure boot with MCUBoot on bare-metal devices

We achieve secure booting using MCUBoot by implementing a series of steps that ensure the integrity and authenticity of the firmware on our nRF52840 devices. The process begins with the manufacturer signing the hashed firmware image using a private key. This signed firmware, along with the corresponding public key, is then stored on the device. When the device boots, MCUBoot initiates the boot sequence and reads the firmware from memory. It computes the hash of the firmware image and uses the stored public key to decrypt the signature, revealing the original hash value that was signed with the private key. MCUBoot then compares the newly computed hash with the decrypted hash. If the hashes match, the firmware is verified as authentic and trusted, allowing MCUBoot to proceed with booting the device securely. If the hashes do not match, MCUBoot halts the boot process to prevent the execution of untrusted firmware, thereby maintaining the security and integrity of the device.

Our current setup involves the Nordic nRF52840 Development Kit (DK) running the Zephyr Real-Time Operating System (RTOS). The application in use is relatively straightforward, consisting of two threads, each responsible for toggling a specific LED. For trace collection on these low-end devices, we are utilizing Segger SystemView via USB. This setup allows us to monitor and analyse the system's behavior effectively, ensuring that our basic functionality is correctly implemented and traceable.

Looking ahead, we plan to explore connections with other ENTRUST components using communication methods such as Bluetooth Low Energy (BLE). This will enable seamless integration and interaction within the ENTRUST ecosystem. Additionally, we aim to investigate more complex runtime measurements, such as stack usage information. Enhancing the periodicity of these measurements could significantly improve the accuracy of our complex verification capabilities, particularly in relation to firmware behavior and anomaly detection. Furthermore, we will explore the feasibility of employing such information for control flow integrity attestation on low-end devices, ensuring minimal resource depletion. This research will also involve validating our findings against other types of tracing methods documented in the literature, aiming to establish a robust and efficient tracing mechanism for resource-constrained medical devices.

7 Research plan towards Second Release

In the following tables, we highlight the functionalities of ENTRUST Blockchain and Tracer we plan to have ready for evaluation in the first release of the ENTRUST integrated framework. This is part of D6.1 and will be delivered in M21 of the project. We also describe what functionalities we envision to be implemented for the second release the ENTRUST integrated framework, which will be evaluated in the context of D6.2 and the end of the project.

Table 30: ENTRUST DLT Implementation Status and Research Plan

ENTRUST actions	Description
Finalization of 1st release of ENTRUST Blockchain	All main components of the ENTRUST DLT will be evaluated in the first release of the ENTRUST integrated framework, towards supporting the trust policy and the attestation data workflows. ABE and ABAC mechanisms will be fully implemented for the 2nd release of ENTRUST DLT.
ABAC	For the 1st release of ENTRUST DLT, exemplary attribute access policies are implemented. The full set of access control mechanisms based on Verifiable Presentations will be implemented in the 2nd release.
ABE	The attribute-based encryption mechanisms that will be leveraged in the ENTRUST DLT, will be fully developed in the 2nd release.
SCB	The SCB will be ready for the evaluation of the 1st release of the ENTRUST integrated platform where the communication of the Nodes with the DLT channels will be monitored. The integration with the full ABAC mechanisms will be evaluated in the 2nd release.
Smart contracts	The smart contracts for recording of attestation data and trust policies in the ENTRUST DLT are developed in the 1st release. The full set of smart contracts, as described in Chapter 5 of this document, will be developed in the 2nd release.

Table 31: Tracer Implementation Status and Research Plan

ENTRUST actions	Description
Benchmark tracer on low end devices in the context of kardinblu	Our current setup involves the Nordic nRF52840 running the RTOS. The application in use is relatively straightforward, consisting of two threads, each responsible for toggling a specific LED. Our next step is to extract tracers from the firmware of the devices used in the Kardiblu by Kardinero and the FES by Sentio Lab
Retrieve traces from low end devices without a usb dongle	For trace collection on these low-end devices, we are utilizing Segger SystemView via USB. We plan to explore connections with other ENTRUST components using communication methods such as BLE.
On demand secure boot verification	Currently, secure boot verification is performed when the device boots. We are in the testing phase to enable the verification process on demand, whenever the attestation process requires it.

<p>Benchmark tracer on high end devices</p>	<p>This research will also involve validating our findings against other types of tracing methods documented in the literature, aiming to establish a robust and efficient tracing mechanism for resource-constrained medical devices</p>
<p>Enhanced runtime and static measurement</p>	<p>We aim to investigate more complex runtime measurements, such as stack usage information. Enhancing the periodicity of these measurements could significantly improve the accuracy of our complex verification capabilities, particularly in relation to firmware behavior and anomaly detection. Furthermore, we will explore the feasibility of employing such information for control flow integrity attestation on low-end devices, ensuring minimal resource depletion</p>

8 Conclusions

In this report, a detailed description of the ENTRUST Blockchain Infrastructure and the Tracer are documented, highlighting the underlying methodologies and components. The general and security requirements, the definitions of the building blocks as well as a set of comprehensive workflows, showing the technical interactions between the ENTRUST components focused on the Blockchain infrastructure and the Tracer are also provided.

In addition, the architecture of the ENTRUST Blockchain including the envisioned smart contract data types and functions have been defined and specified. For the realization of the infrastructure, the selection of Hyperledger Fabric and the rest of the technical components as core elements of the solution are elaborated. Moreover, the functionalities of the Tracer have also been analysed thoroughly.

Last but not least, we concluded this deliverable by providing details of the research and development plan of ENTRUST Blockchain Architecture and Tracer. Thus, the design and development of the first release will drive the integration and evaluation activities for the first ENTRUST integrated framework that will be documented in D6.1, while the new functionalities and updates of the Blockchain Architecture and the Tracer will be documented in the second version of the deliverable, the D5.2.

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